

Efficient water splitting via a flexible solar-powered Hybrid thermochemical-Sulphur dioxide depolarized Electrolysis Cycle

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D2.1 Subsystems requirements for solar platform testing

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WP2 - Process design, simulation and techno-economics

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Preface

HySelect will demonstrate the production of hydrogen (H₂) by splitting water via concentrated solar technologies (CST) with an attractive efficiency and cost, through the Hybrid Sulphur cycle (HyS). The HyS consists of two central steps: the high temperature -yet below-900°C -decomposition of sulphuric acid forming Sulphur dioxide (SO₂) and the subsequent low temperature (50-80°C) SO₂ depolarized electrolysis (SDE) of water to produce H₂. HySelect will introduce, develop and operate under real conditions a complete H₂ production chain focusing on two innovative, full scale plant prototype core devices for both steps of the HyS cycle: an allothermally heated, spatially decoupled from a centrifugal particle solar receiver, sulphuric acid decomposition-Sulphur trioxide splitting (SAD-STs) reactor and a Sulphur dioxide depolarized electrolyzer (SDE) without expensive Platinum Group Metals (PGMs). Furthermore, a heat recovery system will be integrated to exploit the temperature difference within the cycle and boost the overall process efficiency. In the course of the work, non-critical materials and catalysts will be developed, qualified and integrated into the plant scale prototype units for both the acid splitting reactor and the SDE unit. Experimental work will be accompanied by component modelling and overall process simulation and culminate with a demonstration of the complete process integrating its key units of a 750kW_{th} centrifugal particle receiver, a hot particles storage system, a 250kW_{th} SAD-STs and a 100kW_e SDE into a pilot plant. Testing for a period of at least 6 months in a large-scale solar tower, driven with smart operation and control strategies, will establish the HySelect targeted efficiency and costs. Finally, an overall process evaluation will be carried out in order to assess the technical and economic prospects of the HySelect technology, directly linked to the know-how and developments of the sulphuric acid and water electrolyzers industries.

DLR	German Aerospace Center	DE	
CERTH	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	GR	
AALTO	Aalto University	FI	
ENEA	Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development	IT	
FENR	FEN Research GmbH	AT	
GRILLO	Grillo Werke AG	DE	

Summary

This document describes the process analysis carried out over the first year of the HySelect project, with the aim of evaluating different concepts for the flexible hydrogen production via the Hybrid Sulfur (HyS) cycle powered by solar energy. The analysis was built on the outcomes of relevant previous research projects, considering the technological advancements and the specific innovations proposed within HySelect Project. For each process section, possible alternative process solutions have been studied, defining the associated advantages and limitations in terms of energy efficiency, technical viability, controllability, and material compatibility, which finally allowed to select the most promising process options in view of the demo plant realization and testing. Particularly, based on the process analysis reported in the previous paragraphs and considering the specific constraints for the realization of the demo plant (space limitations, safety rules, intermittent operation, etc), in the present study a preliminary process scheme for the whole demo plant has been conceived, as a starting point for the iterative definition of the Process Flow Diagram and the elaboration of a provisional control logic.

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1. Introduction

This document describes the process analysis carried out over the first year of the HySelect project within the Work Package 2 (Process design, simulation, and techno-economics) and more specifically it reports the results of Task 2.1, which is focused on the definition of efficient and viable plant concepts for flexible hydrogen production via the Hybrid Sulfur (HyS) process. Within this Task, a substantial revision and update of the process solutions envisaged for the HyS cycle in the context of previous research projects (e.g. SOL2HY2¹, PEGASUS²) has been performed, considering the specific technological and operational constraints associated with the HySelect innovations (development of allothermally heated high temperature reactors and realization of Sulphur dioxide depolarized electrolyzer (SDE) without expensive Platinum Group Metals), and taking into account the market related information provided by the industrial partner (GRILLO).

Compared to the original HyS (or Westinghouse) cycle, which was proposed in the 1970s as a water splitting process for hydrogen production powered by high temperature nuclear heat and electric power [1], the HySelect process aims at producing completely renewable and carbon-free hydrogen, replacing the nuclear source with the solar source; in order to achieve this goal, technological and process issues, mainly related to the intermittent nature of the solar source, must be solved.

The original HyS cycle is based on the two following reactions:

Rxn.1 is a catalytic thermochemical reaction that is carried out in two steps, as described in the next paragraph: the first one produces SO₃ and water and is almost quantitative at 500°C, whereas the second one is a catalytic step taking place above 800°C, producing SO₂ and O₂.

Rxn. 2 is an electrochemical reaction, where SO₂ is sent to the anode space and is oxidized electrochemically leading to sulfuric acid and hydrogen evolution at cathode. This reaction has a very low standard potential E₀ (~0.16 V) in comparison with the water electrolysis (~1.23 V) at 25 °C [2][3], and this allows to significantly reduce the power input to the overall water splitting process.

The HySelect process, compared to the original HyS cycle, aims at developing and demonstrating new technical solutions for both reactions; particularly, on one side, it proposes the coupling of the chemical process with the intermittent solar source through a robust particle-based solar receiver integrated with a two-tank storage system powering the high temperature Sulphuric Acid (SA) decomposition section, whereas for the SDE, it focuses on the optimization of materials and operational parameters.

Figure 1 shows a simplified block diagram of the whole HySelect process: the H₂SO₄ produced through Rxn. 1 is concentrated, evaporated, and then decomposed to produce SO₂ and O₂, which are separated for recycling back the SO₂ to the SDE unit, as represented in the scheme. Particularly, the figure highlights that the chemical plant, which is mainly composed of i) high temperature SA decomposition section, ii) sulphur dioxide/oxygen separation section, iii) SDE section and iv) SA concentration section, is interconnected with the solar plant through innovative high temperature heat exchangers powered by hot particles and that the process design is aimed at maximizing the internal heat recovery. It is worth noticing that, in the presence of an external SO₂ source, like flue gas from combustion processes, the process can be profitably opened to produce H₂ and H₂SO₄ [4], as represented in Figure 1.

¹ <https://sol2hy2.eucoord.com/>

² <https://www.pegasus-project.eu>

In the next paragraphs, the initial process analysis carried out within Task 2.1 for each process section is described, considering alternative process solutions and identifying the most promising in terms of efficiency, materials compatibility, technical viability and equipment availability.

For the process analysis, the Aspen Plus process simulator has been used as modeling and simulation tool. Particularly, for the SA decomposition and SA concentration sections, the ElecNRTL model has been adopted to describe the physical and chemical equilibria of the $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ thermodynamic system, as proposed by General Atomics [5]; this model is an electrolytic variation of the NRTL model, involving the description of ionic associations and dissociations along with pure component and pair-wise parameters for the ionic and non-ionic components [6]. For the SO_2/O_2 separation section the equation of state approach has been selected, adopting the Redlich–Kwong equation for the description of V-L equilibrium of the SO_2/O_2 thermodynamic system.

Figure 1 - Conceptual scheme of the HySelect process

2. Sulphuric Acid decomposition

The main reactions taking place in the high temperature section of the HySelect process are below reported:

- Sulfuric Acid Dissociation (SAD)

- Sulfur Trioxide Splitting (STS)

These two reactions are intended to be performed in the same reactor working at different temperatures: concentrated sulphuric acid (SA) from the storage unit is vaporized and driven first through a medium-temperature zone (e.g., 500°C) where its stoichiometric dissociation into steam and SO₃ takes place; the vapours mixture is then passed through the catalytic reactor at higher temperatures (e.g. 900°C) where the STS reaction is performed. The innovative reactor design proposed by DLR will be based on a shell & tube configuration, where hot solid particles flow in the reactor outer section to transfer high temperature heat to the reactant gases, which pass through the inner section. This new reactor design is meant to be coupled with the innovative centrifugal receiver CentRec[®] developed and patented by DLR, where inexpensive bauxite ceramic solid particles are used as heat transfer fluid and storage medium up to >1000 °C, thus decoupling the solar energy harvesting and the endothermic process.

2.1. SAD and STS reactors

At the selected temperature interval (450-500°C), the SAD reaction can be considered quantitative, whereas the SO₃ splitting reaction does not achieve complete conversion and the actual SO₃ conversion depends both on thermodynamic limitation and reaction kinetics; however, its maximum value is limited by thermodynamic equilibrium conditions, which in turn depend on temperature, pressure, and composition of the reactor feed. Indeed, a mixture of steam and SO₃ is fed to the STS section whose composition depends on the concentration level fixed in the SA concentrator and the presence of recycled streams.

Assuming that the dissociation reaction is carried out in a reactor approaching isothermal conditions, the corresponding SO₃ equilibrium conversion at different temperatures and initial SO₃ mol fractions, and consequently initial H₂SO₄ concentrations, can be derived from Figure 2. As abovementioned, the SAD-STS reactor demonstrator that is being developed in the HySelect project substantially consists in a heat exchanger powered by the hot particles flowing in counter current and delivering the high temperature solar heat in a temperature interval. From a thermodynamic standpoint, this type of reactor, even if characterized by a significant difference between the inlet and outlet temperatures of the streams, can be approximated by an isothermal reactor operating at the gas outlet temperature. Considering that the hot particles enter the SAD-STS reactor at approximately 900°C, and assuming that the temperature difference between the inlet particles and the outlet gas is comprised in the range 50-100 °C, the outlet gas temperature should vary between 800 and 850°C. In the followings, a reactor outlet temperature of 800 °C for the products will be conservatively assumed. Furthermore, considering an inlet sulphuric acid concentration equal to 75%, leading to an equilibrium SO₃ conversion slightly higher than 0.85 (see Figure 3),

and assuming an approach to equilibrium of 75%, an effective SO_3 conversion of 0.63 will be assumed.

Figure 2 - Calculated equilibrium conversion for SO_3 isothermal decomposition varying the inlet SO_3 molar fraction ($P: 1 \text{ atm}$) – Aspen Plus simulation assuming isothermal equilibrium reactor.

2.2. SO_3 separation

As above mentioned, due to thermodynamic limitations, the SO_3 splitting reaction carried out in the STS does not attain complete conversion and SO_3 is present in the outlet reactor stream also in a considerable amount. Unreacted SO_3 must be separated together with H_2O downstream of the STS and recycled to the reactor feed in order to increase the overall conversion and save energy. Furthermore, separation is clearly needed to obtain pure SO_2 to be fed to the SDE.

Due to the high difference in dew point of sulphuric acid vapour compared to SO_2 and O_2 , separation of SO_3 and H_2O downstream of STS is theoretically simple since cooling to ambient temperature should be sufficient to obtain an almost complete separation. However, this operation entails several process and plant issues that must be managed to guarantee safe operation and efficient heat recovery.

According to the current concept, the outlet stream from the SAD-STS reactor contains the products SO_2 and O_2 , unreacted SO_3 and H_2O at close-to-ambient pressure and temperature in the range 800-850°C. Upon cooling, SO_3 and H_2O react in the gas phase according to the reaction expressed in eq. 1 (in the exothermic pattern). This reaction does not require a catalyst and the reaction extent can be calculated by considering equilibrium conditions. Figure 3 shows the calculated conversion of SO_3 and water into H_2SO_4 at ambient pressure as a function of temperature. Above 600°C, Sulphuric Acid is completely dissociated into SO_3 and H_2O , while around its boiling point at atmospheric pressure, i.e. between 300 and 350°C, SA is mainly present in the undissociated form. Therefore, the cooling process of the STS outlet stream from 800°C to 200°C leads to the complete conversion of SO_3 and water into H_2SO_4 with the release of high temperature heat, and the operation can be conceptually divided in three steps: i) from 800 °C to SA dew point (see Figure 4), subtraction of sensible and

reaction heat from the gas; ii) from dew point to bubble point, subtraction of the latent heat of condensation of H_2SO_4 (see Figure 4); iii) from dew point to the final temperature, subtraction of sensible heat from the liquid. Obviously, with the aim of increasing the process efficiency, the heat released in the cooling step should be recovered within the process. In this perspective, the easiest approach is to use this heat to vaporize/pre-heat the SAD inlet stream.

Therefore, the process analysis of the SO_3 separation step and the SAD-STS unit is integrated and conducted in combination.

Figure 3 - Calculated conversion of SO_3 and H_2O into H_2SO_4 varying the reaction temperature at initial water mole fractions $y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ (atmospheric pressure - Aspen Plus simulation).

Figure 4 - Dew and bubble point for the binary $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ at atmospheric pressure (Aspen Plus simulation).

Two strategies can be followed to recover heat and unreacted component (SO_3) from the high temperature STS reactor outlet stream and recirculate it to the reactor's feed:

- **Indirect contact heat exchange.** In this case, heat transfer is performed by using heat exchangers without mixing the STS high temperature outlet stream with the low temperature SAD inlet stream. This may be the simplest way of carrying out this operation, even if not necessarily the most efficient. Gas phase heat transfer equipment is quite conventional, even if the selection of materials must be considered carefully to avoid corrosion problems. SA condensers most likely are the critical unit in this case. The reference process schemes for this heat transfer strategy are below shown, both in a simplified heat recovery solution (Figure 5) and in an optimized heat recovery configuration (Figure 6). The associated mass balance, derived from process analysis carried out using Aspen Plus process simulator, and referred to the optimized heat recovery configuration **with a capacity of 1 mole/s of SO_2 produced in the STS part of the reactor**, is reported in Table 13 (Annex section). It is worth noticing, for the latter configuration (Figure 6), that the heat exchanger HE1.2 actually has to be considered as a system of heat exchangers (at least two) connected in series, since the condensation of the STS outlet gases and the vaporization of the SAD feed, which take place in HE1.2, pose technical issues in terms of materials compatibility and equipment design. Indeed, as represented in Figure 7, in the temperature interval considered for the two streams (800-180°C for stream 106 and 155-295°C for stream 103) the partial condensation of the hot gas and the complete vaporization of the cold liquid take place. Furthermore, it is worth evidencing that, in the low temperature section of the heat exchanger, a quite limited temperature difference between the hot and cold streams is present: this temperature difference, as represented in Figure 8 is not higher than 10°C. These technical aspects have to be carefully considered in the next steps of the project development, in view of the design of these “unconventional” process equipment.

Figure 5 - SA evaporation and dissociation & SO_3 splitting (in blue frame) and SO_3 separation section (in orange frame): indirect contact heat exchange scheme (simplified heat recuperation).

Figure 6 - SA evaporation and dissociation & SO₃ decomposition (in blue frame) and SO₃ separation section (in orange frame): indirect contact heat exchange scheme with optimized heat recovery.

Figure 7 - Temperature vs. transferred heat in the HE1.2 heat exchanger system.

Figure 8 - Detail of the low temperature section of the HE1.2 heat exchanger.

- **Direct contact heat and mass exchange.** Another possible way to separate SO_3 is by direct contact of the STS reactor outlet stream with fresh feed, i.e., by scrubbing the outlet reactor stream with liquid SA (Figure 9). Indeed, both SO_3 and H_2O are easily and selectively absorbed in liquid SA and this operation is one of the main steps of the contact process used to produce concentrated SA industrially. In this regard, it is worth mentioning that this process solution is adopted by the HySelect industrial partner (Grillo) to separate SO_3 and dust from SO_2 containing gases in sulphuric acid processing plants (Figure 10). In this case, diluted sulphuric acid (not more than 35%_{wt}) at room temperature is used as liquid absorber in the washing column and the outlet gas stream has a quite limited temperature (below 35°C). Furthermore, absorption with SA was also previously considered in the literature for the separation of SO_3 from the STS outlet stream in two thermochemical processes: the Cristina process [7] and the sulphur-iodine (SI) process [4].

This approach would offer one main advantage: simultaneous heat and mass transfer between the reactor's feed and outlet streams, so that it would be possible to carry out in a single step:

- sensible, reaction and latent heat recovery
- recycling of unconverted reactants

Both in the contact and Cristina processes, SO_3 is absorbed in azeotropic (i.e., 98% by weight) liquid SA, while in the HySelect process, lower SA concentrations should be considered.

When gaseous SO_3 is contacted with lower concentration liquid SA, reaction (1) may become difficult to control and lead to the formation of acid mist which is hard to separate [8]. Furthermore, also temperature and corrosion problems could represent an issue. It is worth noting that the same problem does not arise if reaction (1) occurs progressively in a gas phase containing H_2O , like in the indirect contact approach, or in correspondence of diluted sulphuric acid, like in the Grillo's process. A possible solution to overcome these issues in the HySelect process is the adoption of the diluted sulphuric acid produced by the SDE as the liquid absorber in the washing column, in order to make the column's operating condition less severe (SA concentration and temperature). However, this process solution, even if applicable for SO_3 separation from SO_2 , would not be effective in terms of heat recovery since the high temperature heat of the gaseous stream from STS would be substantially degraded and not used to pre-heat the SA feed.

Figure 9 - SA evaporation & dissociation SO_3 splitting (in blue frame) and SO_3 separation section (in orange frame): direct contact heat exchange scheme.

Figure 10 - Conceptual scheme of Grillo's industrial process for SO_3 separation from SO_2 containing gases.

Another possible solution to mitigate the severe operating conditions of the absorption column is to reduce the temperature of the gaseous inlet stream to the column (stream n. 8) transferring directly the high temperature heat of the STS outlet (stream n. 7) to the SAD inlet (stream n. 4), as represented in Figure 11. The heat and mass balance associated with this process configuration is reported in Table 14 (Annex, referred to 1 mol/s of SO₂ produced in the STS reactor).

Figure 11 - SA evaporation & dissociation, SO₃ splitting (in blue frame) and SO₃ separation section (in orange frame): direct contact heat exchange scheme with alternative heat recovery configuration.

Considering that the SAD-STS in the demo HySelect plant, which relies on high temperature solar heat supplied by the hot particles coming from the hot storage unit, is designed to be operated intermittently and will require frequent startup and shutdown operations, the direct contact heat exchange approach seems less viable than the indirect one, especially because a liquid absorption column cannot easily afford such discontinuous operating regime. Adding to that are issues arising from possible restrictions of height imposed by the available space on the platform as well as other practical limitations and the overall complexity of operation of such a column (packing, liquid cycle pumped in a loop, etc.)

Therefore, the indirect contact approach (Figure 6, Table 13 in Annex) is chosen as the most appropriate for the HySelect demo plant while the direct contact will be further analysed in the future in view of the techno-economic optimization foreseen in Task 2.3.

2.3. Temperature profiles in the SAD and STD reactor

As mentioned in the previous paragraphs, reactions (1) and (2) will take place in the same reactor but in two different zones, working at different temperatures. The reactor has a shell & tube configuration,

where hot solid particles flow in the shell, while gases pass inside the tubes (Figure 12). The inlet hot particles directly come from the hot storage tank, whose nominal operating temperature is 900°C, whereas the cold outlet particles are meant to be collected in the cold storage tank, whose nominal operating temperature has been preliminary fixed as 400°C.

Figure 12 - Conceptual scheme of solid particle loop integrated in the SAD/STD reactors.

In order to preliminary assess the operating condition of the SAD and STS systems, which most probably will be integrated in the same equipment, in this work a simplified calculation of the temperature profiles in the two heat exchangers/reactors has been performed, based on the data reported on Table 1, which are referred to the process scheme represented in Figure 6, and assuming a single one-pass counter-current design for the two heat exchangers/reactors.

It is worth noticing that the thermal duty of the STS reactor has been divided in two contributions: (I) the sensible heat required to heat up the gas from 500 to 800°C and (II) the heat of reaction at 800°C (as above mentioned, the catalytic STS reactor is assumed to work in isothermal conditions at the gas outlet temperature (800°C)). For the SAD reactor, on the contrary, as a first approximation, it is assumed that the H_2SO_4 decomposition takes place continuously from 300°C to 500°C; therefore, the SAD thermal energy required, as shown in Table 1 includes both the heat of reaction and the sensible heat. The particle thermophysical properties relevant to the calculation, along with the nominal operating conditions for the thermal storage units are reported in Table 2.

Assuming that the hot particles enter the STS reactor at 900°C and flow in counter-current with the cold gases, and assuming that the thermal energy transfer from the hot particles to the cold gases takes place without energy losses, the temperature of the outlet particle stream has been calculated varying the particle flow-rate from 0.8 to 2 kg/s. The output of this parametric analysis is reported in Table 3, where, beyond the particle outlet temperature, also the minimum temperature difference between the hot particles outlet and the cold gas in the reactors is shown (ΔT_{\min}).

Table 1: Operating conditions of the SAD and STS reactors (thermal energy required referred to 1 mol of SO₂ produced)

Parameter	SAD Reactor	STS Reactor (I)	STS Reactor (II)
Gas Inlet temperature [°C]	295	500	800
Gas Outlet temperature [°C]	500	800	800
Thermal energy required [kJ/mol _{SO2}]	220	104	94

Table 2: Properties of the particles and nominal operating conditions of the thermal storage.

Parameter	SAD Reactor
Particle Bulk density [kg/m ³]	2100
Particle Specific heat [J/kg °C]	1200
Nominal hot particle storage temperature [°C]	900
Nominal cold particle storage temperature [°C]	400

Table 3: Parametric analysis of the particle stream operating condition for SAD/STD reactors varying the particle flow rates.

Particle Mass flow rate [kg/mol _{SO2}]	ΔT_{\min} [°C]	Particle Outlet Temperature [°C]	STS	Particle SAD Outlet Temperature [°C]	Particle residual enthalpy [kJ/mol _{SO2}]
0.80	2.0	693.8		464.6	62.0
0.90	12.9	716.7		513.0	122
1.00	21.6	735.0		551.7	182
1.10	28.7	750.0		583.3	242
1.20	34.7	762.5		609.7	302
1.30	39.7	773.1		632.1	362
1.40	44.0	782.1		651.2	422
1.50	47.7	790.0		667.8	482
1.60	51.0	796.9		682.3	542
1.70	53.9	802.9		695.1	602
1.80	56.4	808.3		706.5	662
1.90	58.7	813.2		716.7	722
2.00	60.8	817.5		725.8	782

From Table 3, it is evident that, in order to allow for a ΔT_{\min} which is higher than 35°C, the particle flow rate has to be higher than 1.2 kg/mol_{SO2}, which corresponds to a particle outlet temperature of about 610°C (see Figure 13 for reactors temperature profile). If the ΔT_{\min} is reduced to 22°C, the particle flow rate has to be about 1 kg/mol_{SO2}, corresponding to a particle outlet temperature of about 552°C. In this regard, in Figure 14, the resulting minimum temperature difference and the particle outlet temperature varying the inlet particle flow rate is shown. These preliminary results, which will be revised once a more detailed design of the SAD-STs reactor and a better estimation of the heat transfer efficiency are available, suggest using the residual enthalpy of the “cold” particles to supply thermal energy to other process section (i.e., SA concentration section, see Figure 15). Indeed, the residual enthalpy of the “cold” particles (reported in Table 3, 4th column), which exit the SAD reactor at about 550-650°C and are meant to be stored at 400°C, can be used to produce steam or to heat up an intermediate HTF (diathermic oil) serving the SA concentration section. In this regard, the temperature level (~550-

650°C) and the available residual enthalpy (around 200-400 kJ/mol_{SO₂}) of the particle outlet stream are perfectly suitable for supplying thermal energy to the SA concentration equipment (single evaporator/distillation column/multistage evaporator), allowing to almost completely “solarize” the HySelect process through the provision of solar heat.

Figure 13 - Temperature vs. transferred heat in the SAD and STS reactors in correspondence of particle mass flow rate equal to 1.2 kg/s (DT_{min} : 35°C) – 1 mole SO_2 produced.

Figure 14 - Minimum temperature difference (ΔT_{min}) and outlet particle temperature as a function of the particle mass flow rate for 1 mol SO_2 produced.

Figure 15 - Conceptual scheme of solid particle loop integrated in the SAD/STD reactors with additional cooling step.

3. SO₂ separation and storage

In the HySelect process, the separation of SO₂ from O₂ is carried out downstream of SO₃ separation with the aim of recycling SO₂ to the SDE and obtaining O₂ as a valuable process co-product.

The technology of SO₂ removal from gaseous streams is quite consolidated, particularly in the field of purification of combustion effluents, which are generated upon oxidation of sulphur compounds typically contained in any fuel. Therefore, several process options for different inlet and target SO₂ concentrations are virtually available on the market.

On the other hand, all the consolidated processes for SO₂ removal are aimed at purifying gaseous streams which contain small amounts of SO₂ (few percent on mole basis), achieving final concentration levels in the tens of ppm range.

On the contrary, due to the high concentration of SO₂ and O₂ in the gaseous stream (approximately 0.6 and 0.3 mol/mol, respectively), the separation process required in the hybrid sulphur cycles is basically a bulk separation. Consequently, the operating conditions and the equipment design to be here considered are significantly different from conventional SO₂ separation processes, even if the basic principles of consolidated purification treatments can be applied.

Most of the conventional SO₂ purification processes require the contact of the SO₂ containing gas with a sorbent that can be regenerated or disposed (as a waste or as a by-product), depending on how the sorbent is treated after it has removed SO₂. Obviously, for the HySelect process, any non-regenerative process should be excluded, since, due to the high concentration of SO₂ in the gas, if sorbent regeneration is not carried out, high amounts of fresh sorbent would be continuously required.

Theoretically, several technical solutions are available, including SO₂ separation by water absorption, SO₂ liquefaction, pressure swing adsorption (PSA), temperature swing adsorption (TSA), membrane separation. The choice depends on different factors and boundary conditions, such as:

- **Operational regime:** thermal energy storage (TES) ideally allows to operate the plant continuously, but nevertheless, processes with lower start-up times may be preferable. However, it is sufficient to ensure that the characteristic start-up time is significantly lower than the characteristic uninterrupted operation time. As an example, staged gas-liquid contactors (e.g., absorption columns), which have start-up times of the order of hours, are not suitable for operation with daily discontinuities, but can be implemented if the plant is expected to run several days without interruption.
- **SO₂ storage type:** SO₂ storage is not required for steady, closed-cycle operation. However, SO₂ storage appears as an important piece of equipment that should be included to buffer fluctuations in the operating conditions and provide sufficient operational flexibility; furthermore, SO₂ storage is unavoidable in case of open-cycle operation or when the high- and low-temperature parts of the plant must be decoupled (e.g., continuous SDE and discontinuous SAC). If present, SO₂ storage is placed downstream of the SO₂ separation process, and the type of storage selected affects the type of separation process to be implemented:
 - Liquid (pure or wet): Best option when SO₂ compression and liquefaction is applied. PROS: lowest storage volume (liquid SO₂ density: 1461 kg/m³), pure SO₂ is not corrosive; CONS: when operating the SDE at atmospheric pressure, dissolving SO₂ in the anolyte requires a further gas-liquid contactor.
 - Liquid H₂O/SO₂(/H₂SO₄) solution: best coupled with water absorption. PROS: it is possible to store the anolyte solution ready to be fed to the SDE; CONS: low storage density (up to two orders of magnitude lower than pure liquid SO₂), corrosion issues.
 - Gaseous SO₂: this option has to be discarded due to low storage density.
- **Open/closed cycle operation:** as highlighted above, open-cycle operation requires SO₂ storage. In this case, liquid SO₂ storage seems the best option as the storage tank will also serve as feeding point for the external SO₂.
- **SDE feed specifications (e.g., purity, O₂ tolerance, etc.):** SDE can tolerate O₂ in the anolyte up to saturation. However, O₂ can chemically oxidize the SO₂ in the catholyte and reduce the efficiency of the process. Therefore, O₂ concentration should be kept as low as possible;
- **Water tolerance:** the presence of small amounts of water in liquid SO₂ leads to severe corrosion issues. In the industrial applications, the maximum allowed water content in liquid SO₂ is 100 ppm (by weight). Therefore, the water contained in the SO₂ enriched stream should be substantially removed before SO₂ liquefaction and storage;
- **Technological maturity:** it is advisable to focus on mature materials and technologies, as SO₂ separation is not a key element to be developed within the project. Also, practical limitations (available footprint, height, weight, accompanying periphery) as well as safety considerations have to be considered for the final selection of SO₂ separation option.
- **Energy consumption (pumping/compression power):** all the processes considered for SO₂ separation run on electricity only. It is therefore crucial to keep the energy consumption of this section low, not only for the overall energy efficiency, but, even more important, for the thermochemical (or exergy) efficiency of the cycle. \dot{U}
- **SO₂ recovery:** SO₂ recovery is the fraction of SO₂ contained in the gaseous inlet stream which is recovered in the liquid outlet stream. Clearly, it is necessary to push the recovery as high as possible for reducing SO₂ makeup and for limiting SO₂ contamination of the outlet O₂ stream; indeed, SO₂ contamination requires further treating of the O₂ stream to obtain a valuable co-product or, even in the unlikely case in which the O₂ stream is vented, to meet environmental restriction. Thus, SO₂ recovery should be reasonably higher than 99%.
- **O₂ purity:** O₂ purity is the O₂ molar fraction in the outlet O₂ stream. As above mentioned, this specification is fundamental to obtain a marketable (or at least environmentally compatible) O₂

stream. Referring to the current regulations for emissions of sulfuric acid plants, the maximum SO₂ content in gas effluents is approximately 100-300 mg/Nm³, i.e. ca. 35-105 ppm. Clearly, this limitation can be site-specific. Stricter specifications apply to sellable O₂. It is worth noting that, SO₂ purity is not as important as O₂ purity because small amounts of O₂ in the SDE anolyte feed do not cause any significant problems, even if a small reduction of the cycle efficiency may be caused by non-electrolytic SO₂ oxidation in the liquid phase.

In the following part of this section, some options for SO₂ separation are analysed, and their pros and cons are highlighted. It is important to underline that in the analysis of this unit, focus will be mainly put on SO₂ recovery, which is more relevant for the HyS cycle, rather than O₂ purity. However, meeting the specification on SO₂ recovery will also ensure a low SO₂ contamination of the O₂ stream. Should a further SO₂ abatement be required to obtain a sellable product, one of the conventional solutions for purification can be implemented.

3.1. SO₂ absorption

Water absorption

Water absorption of SO₂ is the most obvious option to remove SO₂ from an inert gaseous stream and is commonly applied to gas effluent treatment to remove small quantities of SO₂. Application to bulk SO₂ separation has been previously considered for HyS cycle applications by Gorenssek et al. [9] and Guerra-Nierhof et al. [10]. In this process, the gaseous stream is contacted with liquid water and, due to significantly higher solubility of SO₂ in water compared to O₂, SO₂ is preferentially transferred to the liquid phase and removed from the gas. SO₂ dissolution in water follows a combined physical and chemical mechanism, the solubility being enhanced by the following chemical reaction that occurs in the liquid phase.

SO₂ solubility in water data are reported in the literature in several works [11] [12] [13]. Despite the partially chemical nature of the absorption mechanism, SO₂ solubility in water follows a fairly linear trend with SO₂ partial pressure in the gas over a reasonably wide concentration range, so that it can be described with Henry's law, which applies to purely physical absorption:

$$p_{SO_2} = H(T) \cdot x_{SO_2} \quad \text{Rxn. 6}$$

where p_{SO_2} is the partial pressure of SO₂ in the gas phase and x_{SO_2} the molar fraction in the liquid phase. Figure 16 compares the solubility values reported in the literature with predictions obtained with Aspen Plus using SO₂ as Henry component with the following expression for Henry's constant:

$$\ln H = 26.5647 - \frac{2872.96}{T} - 0.30288 \cdot \ln T \quad \text{Rxn. 7}$$

where T is in K and H in Pa. It can be seen that in both partial pressure ranges showed in Figure 16, the agreement of the prediction with the experimental data is satisfactory.

Liquid absorption is a conventional operation in the chemical industry, which is usually carried out in absorption towers where the gas stream is fed from the bottom and the liquid phase flows in counter-current from the top. Gas-liquid contact is ensured by the use of appropriate column internals like sieved plates or packed beds.

Once the SO₂ recovery target is fixed, the minimum liquid water flowrate required to meet the specification can be calculated based on thermodynamic and mass balance considerations. Either an increase of pressure or a decrease of temperature favours the absorption process, so that a lower

amount of water is required; however, significant minimum amounts of water are here required due to high SO_2 concentrations.

Furthermore, due to the high amounts of water required, here a regeneration step is also needed that can be obtained in a second column operating at lower pressure and/or higher temperature.

Based on these considerations, within the Sol2Hy2 project, a process flowsheet for SO_2/O_2 separation by water absorption was developed by DLR (Figure 17, Table 4). This process scheme can be perfectly applied to HySelect cycle since the composition of the SO_2 containing gas (feed stream) is the same. The absorption/regeneration system is operated on a combined pressure and temperature swing approach, particularly the absorption is operated at 12 bar and approximately 40°C , while desorption is operated at atmospheric pressure and approximately 70°C .

The inlet streams are two: i) stream 10, which is the process water and ii) stream 20, which is the SO_2 containing gas, as coming from decomposition section after condensing of water and consisting of SO_2 (66%), O_2 (33%), and H_2O (1%). It is worth noticing that a compression step for the SO_2 containing gas must be considered upstream of stream 20, since the decomposition section is operated at atmospheric pressure, while the absorption column works at 12 atm.

Based on calculations reported in [14], the absorption column has 7 stages: the regenerated washing water from desorption unit (Stream 38) is fed into stage 1, additional process water (Stream 10) is fed into stage 3, while SO_2 -enriched washing water is discharged (Stream 27) at stage 7 (42°C). The clean gas exiting the absorption column (stream 70) consists of almost pure O_2 (99.11%).

The desorption column, operated at atmospheric pressure, has 7 stages, with partial condensation on the top: the vapour distillate (stream 35) contains SO_2 (0.7 mol/mol) and H_2O (0.3 mol/mol), while the bottom stream (stream 37) contains 99.9% of water, to be recycled, after pumping, to the absorption column.

Figure 16 - Experimental data and Aspen Plus prediction for SO_2 solubility in water at 40°C . a) lower pressure range; b) higher pressure range) [14].

Figure 17 - Aspen Plus flowsheet for SO_2 / O_2 separation by water absorption [DLR, [14]]

The section outlet streams are three: i) stream 50, which is the liquified SO_2 rich stream, available as feedstock for the SDE, containing a small amount of water (4% mol), ii) SO_2 -enriched water, available as feedstock for the SDE, containing H_2O (91%mol) and SO_2 (9%mol), iii) stream 70, which is the abovementioned O_2 rich stream, containing O_2 (99.1%), SO_2 (0.57%) and H_2O (0.33%), that has to be further treated to remove the residual amount of SO_2 .

Table 4: Summary of relevant process parameters of scheme represented in Figure 17 [DLR,[14]]. The streams flowrates are normalized to the flowrate of stream 20.

Stream-ID	T °C	p bar	Relative Mass Flow ---	Mole Fraction			Vapor Fraction %
				H2O %	SO2 %	O2 %	
10	40	12	1.58	99%	1%	0%	0%
20	40	12	1	1%	66%	33%	100%
21	40	12	0.69	0%	55%	45%	100%
27	42	12	4.66	96%	4%	0%	0%
29	42	12	2.98	96%	4%	0%	0%
30	89	12	2.98	96%	4%	0%	0%
31	71	1	2.98	96%	4%	0%	5%
32	71	1	2.63	100%	0%	0%	0%
33	71	1	0.35	33%	67%	0%	100%
34	71	1	0.39	33%	67%	0%	100%
35	69	1	0.04	30%	70%	0%	100%
36	90	1	2.59	100%	0%	0%	0%
37	91	12	2.59	100%	0%	0%	0%
38	27	12	2.59	100%	0%	0%	0%
39	71	1	0.39	33%	67%	0%	100%
40	171	3	0.39	33%	67%	0%	100%
41	40	3	0.39	33%	67%	0%	68%
42	40	3	0.05	96%	4%	0%	0%
43	41	12	0.05	96%	4%	0%	0%
44	40	3	0.34	3%	97%	0%	100%
45	197	12	0.34	3%	97%	0%	100%
46	42	12	1.68	96%	4%	0%	0%
47	40	12	1.68	96%	4%	0%	0%
50	40	12	0.31	4%	96%	0%	0%
60	62	12	2.07	91%	9%	0%	1%
70	27	12	0.20	0.33%	0.57%	99.11%	100%

The overall process energy demand is mainly ascribable to the work for compressing stream 20, stream 39 and stream 44. Referring to the production of 1 mol of SO₂, the electricity consumption of each compression step, here calculated using Aspen Plus process simulator, is reported below:

- stream 20 from 1 to 12 atm: 15.0 kJ/mol_{SO₂};
- stream 39 from 1 to 3 atm: 3.0 kJ/mol_{SO₂};
- stream 44 from 1 to 3 atm: 2.8 kJ/mol_{SO₂}.

The overall electricity demand is therefore 20.8 kJ/mol_{SO₂}.

The thermal energy demand, in this process scheme, is associated with the desorption unit operation at low temperature (60-90°C) and has been neglected for the calculation of the overall energy requirement.

It is worth noticing that this process solution is characterized by the circulation of relevant water flows and the management of quite complex pieces of equipment (absorption/desorption columns), not suitable for the demo plant in terms of compactness and controllability. Furthermore, the production of two SO₂ containing solutions at two different SO₂ concentrations (stream 50: 96% mol; stream 70: 9% mol) entails the realization of two separate storage systems to be separately interfaced with the SDE. Additionally, the SO₂ liquified rich stream, which contains 4%mol of water, involves the use of very costly materials for piping and storage tanks since it is highly corrosive. In this regard, in the industrial practice, the purity specification for liquid SO₂ is very high (not more than 100 ppm of H₂O allowed) to improve materials compatibility. Thus, to reduce costs, a dehydration step upstream of the V-L separation in LIQ flash-drum must be included to decrease the water content in stream 50.

Absorption with ionic liquids

Ionic liquids have been recently proposed as a viable and efficient alternative to water for SO₂ absorption in the HyS process [15]. Indeed, these liquids, whose adoption is spreading in several different fields, have very interesting properties useful for such operation; particularly, they exhibit:

- very powerful solvent properties. In some cases, the uptake for gases such as CO₂ and SO₂ can exceed 1 mol of gas per mole of ionic liquid. This allows to operate absorption with much lower liquid flowrates and/or lower operating pressures;
- thermal stability over a reasonably wide temperature range, which allows to operate solvent regeneration by a temperature swing process;
- extremely low vapour pressure, so that they are virtually non-volatile and losses by evaporation are negligible.

With the aim of evaluating the potential advantages associated with the use of ionic liquids in place of water, in the Sol2Hy2 project [14], the absorption capacity of two ionic liquids proposed in the literature as sorbent to separate SO₂ from O₂, namely [EMIm][EtSO₄] [15] and [BMIm][EtSO₄] [16], were compared with water: in Figure 18 the absorption isotherm data for the three liquids at 40°C are reported. From the Figure 18, it is evident that SO₂ has a comparable solubility in the two ionic liquids, while the solubility in water is dramatically lower. Furthermore, in [14], the performance and energy consumption associated with an adsorption column attaining 99% SO₂ recovery using water or one of the selected ionic liquids as solvent were calculated. The results of the analysis are reported in Table 5, which shows that the use of ionic liquids potentially allows to meet the same specifications with much lower solvent rates and operating pressures, leading to a significative reduction of compression and pumping energy consumption.

Regarding the sorbent regeneration step, additional energy must be provided as low temperature heat. As an example, for [BMIm][MeSO₄], regeneration can be carried out at 100-130°C. Assuming to operate absorption at 40°C and 1 atm, about 30 kJ/mol SO₂ are required to bring the ionic liquid to the regeneration temperature [14].

Figure 18 - SO₂ absorption equilibrium data for water and two ionic liquids at 40°C [14].

Table 5: Operating conditions and energy consumption of an absorption column with 4 theoretical stages attaining 99% SO₂ recovery with different liquid solvents [14].

Solvent	Temperature [°C]	Pressure [atm]	Solvent rate [mol/mol SO ₂]	Compression [kJ/mol SO ₂]	Pumping [kJ/mol SO ₂]
H ₂ O	30	1	100.5	-	-
	30	2	52.5	3.6	0.16
	30	5	24.3	8.2	0.3
	30	7	18.9	9.9	0.35
	40	1	134.3	-	-
	40	5	30.6	8.5	0.37
	40	7	23.3	10.1	0.43
[BMIm][MeSO ₄]	30	1	0.83	-	-
	40	1	1.1	-	-
[EMIm][EtSO ₄]	30	1	1.13	-	-

However, possible drawbacks associated with the use of ionic liquids in this process are:

- high viscosity: values from 10 to 500 cP, with strong temperature dependence are reported in the literature;
- high cost: ionic liquids are in general very costly, especially if compared to a very cheap solvent such as water. However, much lower initial amounts and makeup are required for this type of liquid;
- “Unconventional” nature. There is no consolidated experience in large scale industrial applications of this type of fluids.

This latter aspect must be principally considered when selecting the best technical solution for the HySelect process, particularly for the demo plant, since no consolidated experience in the industrial sector can support the design and operation of the absorption/desorption units.

3.2. SO₂ liquefaction by compression and/or refrigeration

As previously mentioned, SO₂ separation by liquefaction and subsequent storage can be considered as a profitable option to interface the HySelect process with external SO₂ sources, in a partial open configuration that co-generates hydrogen and sulphuric acid. Indeed, in the industrial practice, SO₂ is transported as pure liquid in cylinders; therefore, if the HySelect process is designed to manage liquid SO₂, the direct use of external SO₂ is favoured.

In the present work, with the aim of defining possible process solutions for SO₂/O₂ separation by SO₂ liquefaction, the analysis of V-L equilibria of SO₂-O₂ system has been conducted using Aspen Plus process simulator (assuming R-K equation of state).

It is well known that oxygen is far above its critical temperature at ambient conditions, differently from SO₂; it is therefore virtually possible to liquefy and separate SO₂ from O₂ by simple compression. However, in case of a single step compression followed by phase separation, the achievable SO₂ recovery is quite far from the target value (>99%) in the HySelect process. In this regard, in Figure 19, the SO₂ recovery, and also the O₂ purity (i.e. molar fraction) in the gas phase, is represented. As shown in the Figure 19, both parameters benefit from a pressure increase; however, even when compressing the gas up to 15 atm, SO₂ recovery and O₂ purity are lower than 90% and 80%, respectively (if the operation is carried out at ambient temperature). Indeed, to achieve SO₂ recovery higher than 99% at 15 atm, the temperature should be reduced down to -40°C. A further increase of the pressure would not impact significantly on the cooling temperature: as shown in Figure 19, to attain a SO₂ recovery higher than 99%, the temperature should be around -35°C at about 20 atm.

Furthermore, it is worth noting that the final storage pressure should hardly exceed 10-15 atm since, according to [17], a typical mechanical design pressure for SO₂ storage tanks is 15.2 atm, and the actual operating pressure for a maximum operating temperature of 50 °C is about 8 bar.

It is worth evidencing that the above calculations on separation performance are based on a single stage compression and only SO₂ and O₂ (molar ratio 1:0.5) in the inlet stream; however, the main conclusions are valid if a more complex and realistic model of the process is considered. Particularly, to meet the target figures for SO₂ recovery and O₂ purity, it is necessary to chill the inlet feed well below 273 K: this can be achieved either through an external refrigeration loop or by a “self-refrigeration” loop where the refrigerant is the SO₂ itself.

(a) SO₂ recovery considering one single flash; (b) O₂ purity considering one single flash (based on Aspen Plus simulation adopting the R-K equation of state for the calculation of SO₂-O₂ V-L equilibria).

Regarding the option of external refrigeration loop, Figure 20 shows a possible process scheme for the SO₂ separation section which includes an intercooled staged compression (4 stages), followed by a first V-L separation, a cooling at -46°C, and a second V-L separation step. The operating conditions and performance parameters for this process option are reported in Table 6. It is worth noting that the operating conditions here assumed for SO₂ staged compression and refrigeration (P: 7.2 atm and T: -46°C) are quite close to the typical ones of industrial SO₂ liquefaction processes (P: 6 atm and T: 20°C - Grillo's communication). In this latter case, however, SO₂ recovery and O₂ purity values are well below the target HySelect figures, and the outlet gaseous stream (containing approximately 10% mol SO₂) is typically further treated by an additional SO₂ recovery process such as liquid absorption. On the contrary, as already mentioned, in the HySelect cycle, it is necessary to keep the recovery as high as possible to limit the SO₂ makeup and to increase the O₂ purity of the gaseous outlet stream for economic and environmental reasons. Under the operating conditions here assumed (Table 6), the SO₂ recovery is 97.8%, and the O₂ purity is 97.5%, with an overall specific electric consumption equal to 22.37 kJ/mol_{SO₂}. In Table 15 (Appendix) the detailed heat and mass balance referred to this process option is reported.

It is worth noting that, with the aim of reducing the water content in the SO₂ liquified stream below 100 ppm to limit the corrosion issues in the piping and the storage tank, a dehydration column based on the direct contact of the gaseous feed (stream 201) with concentrated SA has been included upstream of the entire section. This technical solution can take advantage of the presence of concentrated SA in the plant, even if the SA concentration required to efficiently remove water from the gas is about 85%; this means that an extra energy consumption should be considered in the overall HySelect cycle to account for the energy demand to concentrate SA from 75% to 85% (as described in section 5.3).

Figure 20 - SO_2/O_2 separation by compression and liquefaction with cooling at -46°C (external refrigeration circuit)

Table 6: Operating conditions and performance parameters of SO_2 staged compression and liquefaction with external refrigeration loop – option n. 1 (close to industrial conditions)

Parameter	Value
Feed pressure [atm]	1
Total compression ratio K2.1 [-]	7.2
Number of stages K2.1 [-]	4
Specific consumption K2.1 [kJ/molSO_2]	11.45
Cooling temperature of stream 210 [$^\circ\text{C}$]	-46
Refrigerant temperature [$^\circ\text{C}$]	-55
Specific consumption external refrigerator [kJ/molSO_2]	11.45
SO_2 recovery [%]	97.8
O_2 purity [%]	97.5
Total specific consumption [kJ/molSO_2]	22.37

With the aim of increasing SO_2 recovery and O_2 purity, a second process scheme has been developed, where the operating conditions of the staged compression and liquefaction are more severe (Figure 21). In this process configurations, the staged compression is split in two steps with an intermediate V-L separation to condensate part of the inlet SO_2 , achieving a final pressure of 14 atm. The compressed gaseous stream is then cooled down to -55°C . The operating conditions and performance parameters for this process option are synthesized in Table 7: the SO_2 recovery and O_2 purity are here equal to 99.3% and 99.1%, respectively, with a total specific electric consumption of $23.56 \text{ kJ}/\text{molSO}_2$. In Table 16 (Appendix) the detailed energy and mass balance referred to this process option is reported.

Figure 21 - $\text{SO}_2\text{-O}_2$ separation by compression and liquefaction with cooling at -55°C (external refrigeration circuit)

Table 7: Operating conditions and performance parameters of SO_2 staged compression and liquefaction with external refrigeration loop – option n. 2 (optimized conditions)

Parameter	Value
Feed pressure [atm]	1
Total compression ratio K2.1 [-]	8
Number of stages K2.1 [-]	5
Specific consumption K2.1 [kJ/mol SO_2]	11.21
Total compression ratio K2.2 [-]	1.75
Number of stages K2.2 [-]	5
Specific consumption K2.2 [kJ/mol SO_2]	2.03
Cooling temperature of stream 210 [$^\circ\text{C}$]	-55
Refrigerant temperature [$^\circ\text{C}$]	-60
Specific consumption external refrigerator [kJ/mol SO_2]	10.32
SO_2 recovery [%]	99.3
O_2 purity [%]	99.1
Total specific electric consumption [kJ/mol SO_2]	23.56

3.3. PSA/TSA separation

Pressure-swing adsorption (PSA) and temperature-swing adsorption (TSA) are two common gas separation processes; in a PSA process, adsorbents are regenerated by reducing pressure whereas in a TSA process, they are regenerated by increasing the operating temperature and supplying heat. PSA/TSA processes are established in the following field:

- Nitrogen and oxygen generation from air (between 1 and 8 bar or between 1 and 0,5 bar absolute – Grillo's communication);
- Air purification (adsorption of moisture and carbon dioxide);

- Hydrogen purification (off-gases from refineries, outlet gas from steam reforming – between 1 and 25 bar absolute);
- Paraffin separation in refineries;
- Solvent recovery (for temperature-sensitive substances).

In the specific application of SO₂ separation, the use of activated carbon, which is one of the most widespread sorbents, is not viable due to possible oxidation by SO₂. Possible alternative sorbents are zeolites, which absorb SO₂, but materials compatibility issues have to be taken into account when considering this option: i) since condensation of water lead to corrosion effect in zeolites (formation of H₂SO₃), a severe drying treatment of the inlet gas has to be performed upstream of the separation unit; ii) a thin layer of alumina should be deposited on zeolites to protect them from the acid environment of the process. Furthermore, capillary condensation of SO₂ in the zeolite pores should be avoided since this disturbs the cyclic adsorption/desorption process and the effective SO₂ uptake. Therefore, PSA, which operates at constant temperature, appears to be most promising. On the other hand, since SO₂ is absorbed by zeolites, it is not withdrawn at the top of the columns at high pressure level, but it is delivered during the desorption process at a low-pressure level. Thus, the compression work is practically lost.

In conclusion, due to the lack of suitable and consolidated sorbents for/in SO₂, PSA/TSA solution does not currently show a sufficient technological maturity for the application at the industrial scale and will be discarded as a solution for the HySelect process.

3.4. Membrane separation

Selectively permeable membranes can be used to separate SO₂/O₂ mixtures. Compared to other gas separation processes, membranes are in general easier to be run discontinuously, which is a very interesting feature for the application in solar powered processes.

Basically, two types of membranes can be used in Sulphur family thermochemical processes: O₂ and SO₂ permeable membranes.

Regarding O₂ permeable membranes, the use of high-temperature oxygen conductors for SO₂/O₂ separation in the SA decomposition reactor have been proposed in the literature [18] [19]. Particularly, yttria-stabilised zirconia (YSZ) dense membranes were considered for their use in integrated membrane reactors, to continuously remove O₂ from the reaction environment, allowing the separation of reaction products, and the increase of conversion at the same time. Anyway, due to the high temperature required, important issues related to the mechanical integrity of this ceramic membranes subjected to discontinuous operation must be considered. Furthermore, a decrease of O₂ permeability during the tests was observed [19], suggesting that also stability issues due to the presence of SO₂ can arise. For these reasons, the use of oxygen conductors in the HySelect process must be discarded.

Regarding polymeric membranes, polyacrylate and cellulose triacetate single layer [20] and composite [21] membranes were previously considered for SO₂ separation. However, even based on Grillo's market survey, this technology is not mature for industrial application and such membrane can be just used for laboratory preparations.

Finally, also ionic liquid supported membranes have been proposed for SO₂ separation [22]. This solution seems very promising, especially for the discontinuous operation suitability. Furthermore, the high absorption capacity and selectivity for SO₂, combined with non-volatility makes ionic liquids perfect candidates as liquid membranes for this separation process. On the other hand, as underlined for other membrane technologies, this solution has not reached a sufficient technological maturity for the application at the industrial level and will not be considered for the HySelect process.

3.5. Conclusions

Different technical solutions were considered for SO₂/O₂ separation: i) absorption by water, ii) absorption by ionic liquids, iii) SO₂ compression and liquefaction, iv) membrane separation, v) PSA/TSA separation. Water absorption and refrigerated SO₂ liquefaction are considered as the most

viable solutions since they are based on conventional equipment which can be reliably designed and scaled up. More innovative processes like ionic liquid absorption or membrane separation appear very promising, especially in view of possible discontinuous operation, but do not currently have a sufficient degree of technological maturity to be considered for the industrial application in the HySelect process. Furthermore, the SO₂ compression and liquefaction process appear more compact and more suitable for demo operation than water absorption since it mainly consists of compressors and flash drums (fast response equipment) and does not substantially entail the use of absorption/desorption columns, except for the dehydration step upstream of the gas compression, which must be carefully considered and revised in the future, also in consideration of techno-economic process optimization. Thus, based on these considerations, the staged compression and liquefaction process has been selected as the reference process for SO₂ separation in the preliminary version of the demo plant scheme.

4. SDE

The Sulphur dioxide depolarized electrolyser (SDE) is one of the key components of the whole HyS cycle, in which the low-temperature step of the process, leading to hydrogen production (Rxn. 2), is carried out.

The SDE is basically a cation-exchange membrane electrolyser, similar to proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolysers used for water electrolysis; indeed, these two types of electrolysers can share the same configuration and use the same membrane materials (e.g., Nafion®).

An aqueous SO₂ solution (inlet anolyte stream) is fed to the anodic space of the SDE, where SO₂ is oxidized to sulfuric acid according to the following semi-reaction:

Protons are conducted across the membrane and transferred to the cathode, where hydrogen is produced according to the following semi-reaction:

An aqueous solution may be fed to the cathodic space (inlet catholyte stream), with the aim of improving the fluid dynamics on the cathodic compartment, reducing diffusional resistances, ease the removal of the produced hydrogen and maintaining the membrane hydration.

Besides protons, components of the anolyte and catholyte solutions can permeate across the membrane. Depending on the operating conditions, water can flow from the anode to the cathode (or vice versa), driven by the combined effect of hydraulic and osmotic pressure gradients as well as by the electro-osmotic drag associated with the proton flow. Sulphur dioxide can diffuse from the anode to the cathode (SO₂ crossover): this phenomenon is detrimental to the SDE performance, as SO₂ reduction to solid Sulphur at the cathode is a parasitic reaction that decreases the efficiency of the electrolyser while causing cathode fouling and, possibly, deactivation. For the same reason, the presence of SO₂ in the inlet catholyte solution must be avoided.

Sulfuric acid is usually added to the anolyte and catholyte solutions, in order to increase their electric conductivity. SA concentration in the electrolyte solutions is one of the key operating conditions of the SDE, which affects its performance as well as the overall efficiency of the HyS cycle: since SA is a product of the anodic reaction, the higher the SA concentration in the anolyte, the higher the required operating voltage (and thus, electricity consumption) of the SDE; however, from a whole cycle perspective, a higher SA concentration in the outlet anolyte stream will reduce the thermal energy required for SA concentration. The SA concentration should therefore be defined based on an overall process optimization.

At this preliminary stage, we are only interested in the overall energy and mass balances in the SDE, i.e., in relating the composition of the anolyte and catholyte and operating conditions to the outlet composition and flowrate of the outlet streams and SDE electricity consumption; to that end, an Excel

spreadsheet was developed (Figure 22), which implements simplified functions provided by AALTO based on a set of simulations carried out with a more detailed model. This simplified metamodeling approach was used to estimate the mass and energy balances over the SDE under the following hypotheses agreed with AALTO:

Operating temperature: 25°C; operating pressure 1 atm

Inlet anolyte (IA) sulfuric acid (SA) concentration: in the range 0.5-60 % w/w (SO₂-free basis)

IA SO₂ concentration: saturation @ SO₂ partial pressure equal to operating pressure

SO₂ conversion: 85-90 % (this does not include permeated SO₂, i.e. SO₂ lost from the anolyte due to membrane crossover)

Faradaic efficiency: 90-95%

SO₂ crossover: as calculated in the Excel spreadsheet. All permeated SO₂ is assumed to be found in the outlet catholyte (OC) stream (Parasitic reactions not included in the mass balances)

Inlet catholyte (IC) stream:

15% w/w SA

Half water flow as in IA

Figure 22 – Spreadsheet for preliminary SDE mass and energy balance calculation

Several simulations were carried out by varying the IA SA concentration in the range 0.5-60 %. The results are shown in Table 8. It can be seen that the electricity consumption increases as the SA concentration in the IA increases, as expected. The optimization of this parameter will be carried out at a later stage by considering the overall cycle efficiency and by using simulations carried out with more detailed models to be provided by AALTO.

Table 8: Parametric analysis of SDE operating conditions

	Variable	Units										
Anolyte inlet	SA molar flow	mol/s	0,04	0,40	0,85	1,36	1,93	2,58	3,33	5,20	7,76	11,34
	H2O molar flow	mol/s	41,39	41,53	41,69	41,85	42,00	42,15	42,27	42,42	42,21	41,13
	SO2 molar flow	mol/s	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00
	SA conc w/w	-	0,46%	4,63%	9,29%	14,00%	18,74%	23,52%	28,34%	38,10%	47,99%	58,01%
	SA conc w/w (SO2-free)	-	0,50%	5,00%	10,00%	15,01%	20,01%	25,01%	30,01%	40,01%	50,01%	60,01%
Anolyte outlet	SA molar flow	mol/s	0,94	1,30	1,75	2,26	2,83	3,48	4,23	6,10	8,66	12,24
	H2O molar flow	mol/s	35,93	36,18	36,48	36,80	37,13	37,42	37,65	37,75	37,13	35,23
	SO2 molar flow	mol/s	0,095	0,095	0,095	0,095	0,096	0,096	0,096	0,096	0,096	0,095
	SA conc w/w	-	12,34%	16,25%	20,57%	24,86%	29,14%	33,42%	37,73%	46,56%	55,71%	65,20%
	SA conc w/w (SO2-free)	-	12,45%	16,38%	20,72%	25,03%	29,33%	33,62%	37,95%	46,79%	55,93%	65,41%
	Cell voltage	V	1,05	1,07	1,09	1,12	1,15	1,18	1,22	1,29	1,38	1,48
	Specific power consumption	kJ/molH ₂	199,8	204,5	210,1	216,1	222,6	229,5	236,7	251,8	267,9	285,0

5. H₂SO₄ concentration

5.1. Single stage evaporation and distillation

The SA concentration section aims at concentrating the mixture consisting of water and sulphuric acid produced by the SDE, upstream of the reactors section, in order to reduce the consumption of high temperature heat in the SAD and STD reactors.

Different process solutions with different levels of complexity are theoretically viable to concentrate SA solution, but, within this work, an accurate analysis of alternative process options, supported by the use of Aspen Plus process simulator, has been performed, also based on the know-how gained within previous project (e.g., SOL2HY2 project), in order to identify a compromise to safety, cost and efficiency.

Based on the initial process conditions fixed for the SDE, the inlet SA concentration is assumed to be in the range of 15-25%_{wt}, while, considering the results from the process optimization performed in the SOL2HY2 project [23] the outlet SA concentrations is assumed equal to 75%_{wt}. Furthermore, while a small amount of SO₂ is expected to contaminate the SDE anolyte outlet stream (approximately 2-3%_{wt}), in the following analysis the presence of SO₂ in the feed of the SA concentration section has been neglected, since a single low temperature heating step, followed by a L-V flash, should be sufficient to separate gaseous SO₂ from the diluted SA stream. This gaseous SO₂ stream can be then absorbed in water and recycled back to the SDE. The process analysis of this recirculation loop will be performed once more consolidated figures are available for the SDE operation.

Taking into consideration the abovementioned assumptions, the simplest process solution for concentrating the diluted SA stream consists of a single evaporator (Figure 23,

Table 16 and Table 18) at room pressure. Nevertheless, this solution consumes a significant amount of energy since the enthalpy of the water steam exiting the evaporator is not recovered (824.96 and 1523.69 kJ/mol_{H₂SO₄} respectively for SA inlet concentration of 15 or 25%).

Figure 23: H_2SO_4 concentration by single evaporation.

To this purpose, a heat exchanger can be integrated downstream of the evaporation (Figure 24) to pre-heat the inlet mixture, but only a small amount of the water steam enthalpy can be recovered, if this section operates at a constant pressure, due to temperature matching issues (Table 19 and Table 20)

Figure 24 - H_2SO_4 concentration by single evaporation and partial heat recovery.

To transfer the steam's latent heat to the SA feed, it is necessary to compress the steam up to 2.6 atm by a compressor installed downstream of the evaporator (Figure 25). Considering the target H_2SO_4 concentrations here assumed (75%_{wt}), and a compression ratio of 2.6, the temperature of the compressor outlet steam is 344 °C. A supplementary heat exchanger to exploit the enthalpy of the concentrated H_2SO_4 mixture can also be integrated into the process to maximize the heat recovery (Table 21 and Table 22). Figure 26 shows the internal heat matching for the inlet SA concentration of 15wt%. It highlights how the pressure of 2.6 atm for a stream consisting in almost totally water can concentrate the mixture of H_2SO_4 and H_2O up to 75w%, including the contribution of the sensible heat of the vapour leaving the compressor. In this way, the stream to be concentrated needs most of the

thermal energy from 84 to 129 °C (from 0 to 82% of vapour fraction), which can be ensured by the stream at 2.6 atm, which cools down from 142 to 129 °C, giving off all its latent heat.

Figure 25 - H_2SO_4 concentration by single evaporation and optimized heat recovery (use of steam compression).

Figure 26 - Detail of E.4.2 heat exchanger showing the internal heat matching.

In any case, using a single evaporation step, the obtained water steam is expected to contain small amount of H_2SO_4 (about 0.25 wt% of H_2SO_4). This does not represent a problem for the overall mass balance, since the very diluted SA stream could be recycled to the SDE, but the presence of small traces of H_2SO_4 in the water steam should be considered for possible materials compatibility issues (particularly for the compressor).

As an alternative, to ensure the separation of pure water steam from concentrated SA, with no recycling of diluted SA streams, a distillation column (Figure 27, Table 23 and Table 24) should be

adopted in place of the single evaporator. This column could be a simple 4-stage packed column equipped with a reboiler, without the top condenser.

Figure 27 - H_2SO_4 concentration by distillation and optimized heat recovery (use of steam compression).

While the schema including the combined use of column and compressor can be considered as the best solution for an industrial plant, for the demo plant the one including evaporator and compressor appears to be the most effective, as a compromise of simplicity and energy consumption, provided that a commercial compressor of the proper size (comprised in the range 35-100 kW, depending on the STS reaction wt conversion and the inlet SA concentration of 15-25wt%) can deal with water steam containing 0.25 wt% of H_2SO_4 at a final temperature of 345 °C.

In the Tables included in the Annex, the mass and energy balances resulting from the process analysis of the above mentioned solutions, conducted by means of Aspen Plus process simulator, are reported (referred to 1 mol of concentrated sulphuric acid produced (75 wt% in a mixture with water) for an inlet SA concentration of 15wt% (Table 17, Table 19, Table 21, Table 23) and 25wt% (Table 18, Table 20, Table 22 and Table 24).

As for the configuration using the distillation column, the total consumption as primary energy source for the compressor has been assessed considering a conversion efficiency from heat to electricity of 0.4.

It is worth noticing that if no SO_2 enters the concentration section, all the related streams aren't expected to include any trace of SO_2 , SO_3 and O_2 .

5.2. Multi-effect evaporation

As above described, the SA concentration based on the use of water steam compression represents the most promising solution in terms of energy consumption, but it is not the most widely used in the industrial field.

Actually, the vapour compression process is usual for H_2SO_4 concentration up to 25 wt.%. At higher concentrations, the boiling point increases along with the SA content in the vapor phase, leading to the possible formation of $\text{SO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ associates. Nevertheless, in the case here considered (atmospheric pressure and 75%wt SA concentration in the liquid phase), the SA content in the vapour phase is very low (0.23% for single-step evaporation and negligible traces for distillation column). Therefore, the above-mentioned vapour compression up to 2.6 atm should not pose any specific technological issue.

For SA high-concentration processes (>90 wt.%), due to the acidity of the vapours from the highly concentrated boiling sulphuric acid, it is necessary to scrub the vapours. This operation is accomplished in a column downstream of the evaporator, using the fed diluted sulfuric acid as absorber; the SA concentration in the resulting condensate is mainly determined by entrained acid droplets and is lower than 1wt% [24].

In any case, the same source [25] reports that for SA concentrations up to 70 wt.%, the most used H_2SO_4 concentration method is the multi-stage evaporation, where the diluted vapour streams exiting the evaporators are exploited to provide heat to the boiling mixture of the following one, operating at lower pressure. The first evaporator can work at room pressure and the others under vacuum. Particularly, the application of a 3-stage plant, where the 3rd stage is heated by the vapour from the 2nd stage, the second stage is heated by the vapour from the 1st stage, and the 1st stage is heated by external steam, is quite widespread, but for the heating, other methods can be applied, such as thermal oil or electrical energy. In any case, the 3rd and 2nd stages are operated under a vacuum.

Up to 70%, the vapour/liquid equilibrium curve of sulfuric acid/water (Figure 28) shows that, in practice, no sulfuric acid is contained in the vapour phase at atmospheric pressure; nevertheless, the content of SA in the vapour phase increases with the pressure [26], as shown in Figure 28.

In addition, the equilibrium temperature increases with the pressure (e.g.: 165°C at 1 bar, 208 °C at 2 bar and 246°C at 5 bar) as shown in Figure 29. The increase of boiling temperature and SA concentration in the vapour phase with the increase of operating pressure, obviously heavily impacts corrosion issues, and consequently, the material cost of the evaporators, as it will be described in the following. On the contrary, above a SA concentration of 85 wt.%, the vapour pressure of sulfuric acid increases significantly, reaching a maximum at 98.5 wt.% (azeotrope) at room pressure.

Figure 28 - $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ equilibrium data at 1, 2 (a) and 5 (b) bar [H_2SO_4 in the feed, H_2SO_4 in the vapour phase]

Figure 29 - H_2O/H_2SO_4 equilibrium data at 1, 2 (a) and 5 (b) bar [H_2SO_4 in the feed vs temperature]

The conceptual scheme of the multi-effect evaporation method, whose mass and energy balance has been performed using Aspen Plus process simulator, is shown in Figure 30 for inlet SA concentration of 15 wt.% (Table 25), 25 wt.% (Table 26) and 45 wt.% (Table 27, Table 28). In this work, the adoption of an evaporation step at atmospheric pressure and two evaporation steps under vacuum has been considered (1, 0.2 and 0.044 atm).

Of course, the E.4.3 outlet steam (408) is expected to go to a condenser to allow the vacuum at 0.04 atm. To this purpose, a “mixing condenser” is suggested, because it is a mature technology and cheaper than other equipment. It consists of a tank with a conic bottom, equipped with plates. When the vapour goes up, it directly contacts the cooling water and condenses, exiting from a barometric discharge.

Nevertheless, a vacuum pump or an ejector must suck the non-condensable gases in the process stream and in the cooling water.

This process configuration entails an external energy demand only for the first evaporator.

Figure 30 - H_2SO_4 concentration by counter-current triple effect evaporation.

5.3. Concentration up to 85wt%

A higher concentration for the SA stream could be required in other process sections, particularly to dehydrate the gaseous stream containing SO_2 and O_2 produced in the STS reactor, as mentioned in Section 3. In this case, a distillation column to be integrated downstream of the SA concentration section should be necessary. Therefore, in the present study, a further concentration step by distillation, which increases the outlet concentration of the SA stream up to 85 wt.%, has been assumed (Figure 31) and a process simulation has been conducted to calculate mass and heat balance (from Table 29 to Table 32). The presence of the condenser (Figure 31a) in the column ensures the almost totally removal of the SA in the distillate; alternatively, also the adoption of a stripping column, with no condenser (Figure 31b), can be considered; in this latter case, an energy demand reduction of about 10% can be achieved, but the resulting vapour stream from the top has a residual amount of SA equal to the 0.2 wt.%. In the above-mentioned tables, the following options are considered: inlet SA concentration at 70.6% and 75%, and presence/absence of the top condenser. It is worth noticing that the heat and mass balances reported in these tables are referred to 1 mol/s of SA, in line with the analysis conducted so far, even if only a fraction of the SA exiting the multi-effect evaporation will be further concentrated (about 38%).

Figure 31 - H_2SO_4 concentration up to 85 wt.% by a distillation column with (a) or without (b) top condenser.

5.4. Process solution selection

To summarize the results of the analysis, Table 9 reports the calculated energy consumption for the different proposed solutions for SA concentration up to 75 wt.%. If a higher SA concentration level is required in view of the overall process optimization, a distillation column to be integrated downstream of the first step of concentration is necessary. In the present work it has been assumed to concentrate the SA stream up to 85 wt.%, corresponding to an additional energy consumption ranging from about 84 to 57 $\text{kJ/mol}_{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}$ (as reported in the Table 30 and Table 32), depending on the column configuration and the inlet SA concentration.

Considering the energy consumption, the process scheme based on the single evaporation coupled with the steam compression seems very promising, but the selection of the most suitable process configuration for the SA section, both for the demo and the full-scale plant, must be based also on other factors, such as the commercial availability of process equipment, controllability, costs, scalability. In the followings, the issue of materials compatibility and commercial availability is discussed.

Table 9: Comparison of energy consumption of the different proposed solutions for the concentration step

Inlet H ₂ SO ₄ concentration	Heat [kJ/molH ₂ SO ₄]			Electricity [kJ/molH ₂ SO ₄]		
	15%	25%	45%	15%	25%	45%
Single evaporation	1524	825	306	-	-	-
Single evaporation and partial heat recovery	1337	690	260	-	-	-
Single evaporation and optimized heat recovery	-	-	-	169	87	40
Distillation and optimized heat recovery	191	87	52	143	74	36
Multi-effect evaporation	553	309	135	-	-	-

Corrosion aspects

Sulfuric acid is known to be very corrosive at high temperatures and in the concentration range from 0.1 to 0.9 by weight. Few materials, such as zirconia and tantalum, can be adopted in all the concentration range. Metal alloys, such as Hastelloy, should be used with caution at concentrations below 90%.

A cost effective solution, capable to deal with concentrated SA, is an alloy obtained from the Tantaline treatment [27]: this material consists in a stainless steel substrate which is treated and covered by a layer of tantalum; the resulting material is an alloy that is excellently resistant to corrosion and can maintain the mechanical characteristics of steel. Tantaline[®] is virtually immune to sulfuric acid corrosion up to a temperature of 175°C. Above this temperature, ceramics materials should be used. According to the studies carried out by Shinji Kubo [28] as part of the evaluation of the corrosion resistance of materials in the Sulphur-Iodine process, it was concluded that SiC, Si-SiC and Si₃N₄ are very resistant to SA solution at high temperatures and medium pressure (<10 bar). It is worth noticing that, if the sulfuric acid is highly concentrated (>90wt%), it is less corrosive.

Available commercial solutions

According to a commercial survey, Dedietch[®] (www.dedietch.com) [29] company, leading global provider of process equipment for the fine chemical, chemical and pharmaceutical industries, provides technological solutions for concentrating SA in the capacity range 100-145000 kg/h (HySelect demo plant size is about 1440 kg/h) using multi-stage evaporators up to 70wt% and multi-stage evaporators + distillation columns for higher concentrations. The concentration process is carried out under vacuum to decrease the SA solution boiling temperature, with the aim of avoiding corrosion issues and to enable the use of steam (typically at 13-17 barg) as heating media for the tantalum tubed heat exchangers. As an alternative to the steam, electrical resistors are proposed as heating element (electrical quartz heating sticks).

The diluted feed acid is pre-heated by hot concentrated sulfuric acid in a heat exchanger which is corrosion-resistant on both media sides. Dedietch[®] proposes the following items for the heat exchanger: tubes made of SiC or borosilicate glass; shell and header made of glass-lined or borosilicate glass, tube plate made of PTFE or PTFE/PVDF with embedded stainless steel plate; PTFE sealings screws and gaskets.

For further cooling of the concentrated sulfuric acid and the condensation of the acidic water, the shell & tube heat exchangers must be corrosion-resistant only on the shell side, so that stainless steel covers and support plates can be used on the cooling water side allowing a cooling water pressure of up to 6bar (source: High concentration of sulfuric acid | De Dietrich Process Systems) [24].

Also, special SiC heat exchangers are commercially available, which can deal with extended H₂SO₄ concentration ranges at very high temperatures. Thanks to the high corrosion resistance of SiC, the

evaporation of the feed can be processed at elevated pressures, obtaining pressurised steam that can be exploited within the process [30].

Process configuration selected

Based on the results and considerations reported in the previous paragraphs, the multi-effect evaporation has been selected as the reference solution for the demo plant and as a promising option in view of the HySelect technology scale up. Indeed, beyond having a quite limited energy consumption, it combines process simplicity with equipment robustness; furthermore, it virtually does not require electricity input, allowing the valorisation of the renewable heat produced by the concentrated solar plant. Finally, it has the advantage of already commercial solutions, suitable for the concentration of SA up to 70-75 wt.%.

On the contrary, single evaporation with/without heat recovery, even if a simple and compact process solution, entails very high energy consumptions and therefore cannot be considered a viable route neither for the prototype nor for the industrial plant. The integration of a compressor downstream of the water evaporation step is a very interesting mean to achieve significant energy savings, exploiting the water latent heat of condensation, but relevant corrosion issues in the compressor are expected for the presence of small traces of SA in the water steam (about 0.3%). The adoption of a distillation column in place of the single evaporator can overcome this issue since pure water steam can be obtained as distillate; on the other hand, the energy consumption, the cost and complexity of this section would significantly increase, as well as the electricity share in the energy demand.

The integration of a stripping column, downstream of the multi-effect evaporation, to concentrate up to 85% a limited part of the outlet SA stream at 70-75%, can be considered a viable solution to provide a very useful dehydrating agent within the HySelect process.

6. Preliminary demo plant definition

Based on the process analysis reported in the previous paragraphs and considering the specific constraints for the realization of the demo plant (space limitations, safety rules, intermittent operation, etc), in the present study a preliminary process scheme for the whole demo plant has been conceived, as a starting point for the iterative definition of the Process Flow Diagram and the elaboration of a provisional control logic. Particularly, as represented in Figure 32, this first version of the demo process scheme is mainly based on the following process solutions:

- 1. SA decomposition: i) ground-level shell & tube reactor, operating at atmospheric pressure and 800°C, powered by hot particles coming from the hot storage tank, ii) electric back-up heater connected with the hot storage tank and the shell & tube reactor to adjust particle temperature in case of prolonged low DNI, iii) indirect contact heat exchange for the cooling and separation of unreacted SO₃ (Figure 6, Table 13);
- 2. SO₂/O₂ separation: i) staged compression and liquefaction of SO₂ at low temperature (-55°C), ii) possible dehydration step, upstream of the gas compression, using concentrated SA solution (85%w/w) as water sorbent (Figure 21, Table 16);
- 3. SDE: i) Sulphur Dioxide-depolarized Electrolyzer operating at moderately high SA concentrations in the anolyte section, to reduce the overall process energy demand; ii) SO₂ mixer, practically consisting in a packed column, to allow SO₂ absorption in the anolyte inlet;
- 4. SA concentration: i) multi-effect evaporation, for a first step SA concentration (approximately to 70-75%w/w) (Figure 30), ii) distillation column, for a second step SA concentration (approximately to 85%w/w) (Figure 31).

To interconnect these sections and guarantee the stable operation of process equipment, four buffer tanks containing water, SA at 75%_{w/w}, SA at 85%_{w/w}, liquid SO₂, have been included in this preliminary scheme. Furthermore, to allow the recovery of the SAD outlet particles residual heat (which exit at about 550-650°C and are meant to be stored at 400°C), an intermediate HTF loop is here envisaged (or, alternatively, a water steam loop) which transfers the recovered heat to the SA concentration section.

The overall heat and electricity demand for the defined demo plant is presented in Table 10, while in, Table 11, a simplified mass balance, which considers the main streams of the HySelect process, is reported: both the tables are referred to a basis case of 1 mol_{SO₂} produced at the splitting reactor and a SDE outlet SA concentration of 45%_{w/w}. The values here reported must be considered as a reference case to ease the scaling of the process to other plant capacities (see Section 6.2).

Table 10: Heat and electricity demand for the HySelect demo plant referred to 1 mol_{SO₂} produced in the SA decomposition section

Net thermal energy demand	[kJ/mol_{SO₂}]
SA decomposition section	426
SA concentration section	146
SO ₂ /O ₂ separation section	-
SDE section	.
TOT	572
Net electricity demand	[kJ/mol_{SO₂}]
SA decomposition section	-
SA concentration section	-
SO ₂ /O ₂ separation section	24
SDE section	252
TOT	276

Table 11: Simplified mass balance for the HySelect demo plant referred to 1 mol/s_{SO₂} produced in the SA decomposition section

	H ₂ O	H ₂ SO ₄	SO ₃	SO ₂	O ₂	H ₂
	mol/mol _{SO₂}					
SA decomposition section						
Inlet concentrated SA	1.82	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Outlet gaseous products	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.97	0.50	0.00
Outlet water	2.77	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00
SA concentration section						
	-					
Inlet diluted SA from SDE	6.67	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Outlet concentrated SA	1.82	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Outlet water	4.85	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO₂/O₂ separation section						
Inlet gaseous streams	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.97	0.50	0.00
Outlet liquid SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.97	0.00	0.00
Outlet O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.00
Outlet water	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SDE section						
Inlet SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.97	0.00	0.00
Inlet water	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Inlet recirculated water	7.67	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00
Outlet H ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
Outlet anolyte	6.67	1.003	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Figure 32 – Initial version of demo plant lay-out

6.1. Preliminary operating and control strategy definition

The operational strategy to be developed for the HySelect demo plant must be primarily aimed at matching the discontinuous operation of the solar plant with the virtually continuous operation of the chemical plant, maintaining the process parameters within an acceptable range of variation for the efficient conversion of the solar radiation into renewable hydrogen. The mismatching of the discontinuous solar plant with the virtually continuous chemical plant is attained through the operation of the thermal energy storage system, consisting of the particle hot tank connecting the solar receiver outlet with the SAD/STS reactor inlet and the particle cold tank connecting the STS/SAD reactors outlet with the solar receiver inlet.

The operating strategy of the integrated HySelect plant is schematized in Figure 33, though a flowchart representing the main rules and decision criteria for managing low-radiation conditions and/or situations of empty/full energy storage. Obviously, these schematic decision criteria will be detailed in the future since each of the considered transitions should be operated adopting specific control strategies for transitory regimes.

For the CSP plant, three operating regimes can be hypothesized:

1. **ON-SUN STORAGE** (usual mode of operation): the heliostat field focuses the solar radiation onto the receiver. The "cold" particle mass flow (max. temperature of 400°C) is heated to the desired temperature. The heated particles are temporarily stored in a hot storage tank and can be fed to the reactor as required. Depending on the design of the reactor, batch feeding or continuous feeding is possible. Regarding the control strategy the decisive factor here is the particle outlet temperature from the receiver, which serves as the central control variable for system operation. In addition to this temperature, the irradiation flux density at the aperture is also measured continuously. This flux density determines the particle outlet temperature. It is set via the solar field by focusing more or fewer heliostats (mirrors) on the aperture depending on the load case. This means that the system is only operated when the irradiation on the solar field is sufficiently high. Otherwise, the system is either in DEFOCUS or in OFF-SUN. The CSP plant is in the "ON-SUN STORAGE" working regime and the following condition is verified:

- the incident power P_{inc} on the receiver is higher than the minimum incident power $P_{inc,min}$.

2. **DEFOCUS**: the solar field is defocused. This operating mode is generally coupled with an emergency shutdown. Such an emergency shutdown can have various reasons: excessive flux density at the aperture, malfunction of the receiver motor, overtemperature at the receiver, hot and/or cold storage tank, transport system, etc. As soon as the corresponding fault is no longer present, the system is operated again.

3. **OFF-SUN**: the CSP plant is inactive, and the following condition is verified:

- the incident power P_{inc} on the receiver is lower than the minimum incident power $P_{inc,min}$.

Regarding the chemical plant, the following operating regimes can be distinguished:

1. **PROCESS RUNNING**: The process is working in nominal conditions, powered by the hot tank; the TES capacity, E_{TES} , is higher than $E_{TES,min}$ (fixed percentage of the maximum TES capacity $E_{TES,max}$). The plant keeps operating and work under nominal conditions up to a minimum TES capacity equal to $E_{TES,min}$, sufficient to guarantee the shut-down operation.

2. **PROCESS STAND-BY:** The process is not working (night-time, absence of operators, possible maintenance operations and/or programmed inspections); the TES capacity, E_{TES} , is higher than the residual TES capacity, $E_{TES,y\%}$, sufficient to guarantee the start-up, the operation of the plant for a fixed number of hours, and then shut down. Therefore, the process can be re-started and can run for a fixed number of hours in nominal conditions.

3. **PROCESS OFF:** The process is not working and TES Capacity, E_{TES} , is lower than $E_{TES,y\%}$: the process cannot be re-started till the TES capacity is higher than $E_{TES,y\%}$.

Figure 33 – Flow chart describing the operating strategy of the HySelect plant

It is worth noticing that, if the minimum TES capacity $E_{TES,min}$ can be considered coincident with the residual TES capacity $E_{TES,y\%}$, the operating strategy can be simplified in the scheme reported in Figure 34.

Figure 34 – Flow chart describing the operating strategy of the HySelect plant – simplified version

Concerning the control logic of the demo plant, the main control loops for each process section have been preliminarily identified within T2.1, selecting principal controlled and manipulated variables, as a starting point for the elaboration and implementation of the plant smart control in WP8.

It is worth noticing that only the principal process parameters (mostly temperature), which directly and significantly affect the efficiency and performance of the main process units, have been here considered, whereas the level and the pressure control in V-L separators/vessels/columns will be explicitly taken into account in the future, for the complete flowsheet and P&ID elaboration.

Regarding the solar plant, a specific control strategy is already available in Julich for the concurrent management of the solar field and the solar receiver, particularly to guarantee safe operation of the solar receiver. Particularly, for the purposes of the HySelect project, the temperature of the solar receiver walls and particle outlet stream is controlled by partial focusing/defocusing of the solar field, as represented in Figure 35.

For the SA decomposition section (Figure 35), the control strategy is mainly aimed at stabilizing the temperature of STS reactor at the target value (800°C) for maximizing SO₃ conversion. Therefore, the controlled variable is the STS gas outlet temperature, whereas the manipulated variable is the flowrate of the inlet sulphuric acid. Furthermore, in order to enable the efficient recirculation of the unreacted SA to the SAD and STS reactors, the concentration of the recirculated stream 109 must be maintained close to the concentration of the stream 101. This can be attained through the control of the S1.1 flash drum temperature by the modulation of the stream 109 flowrate.

Finally, regarding the heat recovery loop conceived for the cold particle, with the aim of stabilizing the temperature of the HTF hot storage, the flowrate of the cold HTF stream entering the HTF/particle heat exchanger is here assumed to be regulated.

Figure 36 – Preliminary definition of main control loops for SO_2/O_2 separation section

Concerning the SDE section (Figure 37), whose definition is still at a preliminary stage, beyond the intrinsic control of SDE parameters (voltage, current, etc), the key operating parameter which appears to significantly affect the overall heat demand is the SA concentration of the anolyte inlet, to be in the range 40-60%_{w/w} to minimize the overall energy consumption. With the purpose of controlling this parameter, the flowrate of the SDE inlet water stream, coming from the water storage, is here considered as the manipulated variable.

Furthermore, the temperature of the subsequent heating step, which separates the unreacted SO_2 from the diluted SA (anolyte outlet), is also controlled by varying the HTF flow-rate. The resulting gaseous SO_2 stream is then cooled before being recycled to the SDE mixer: also in this case, the temperature of the cooling step is regulated by varying the cooling water flowrate. Finally, with the aim of ensuring a stable inlet to the SA concentration section, a three way valve has been positioned downstream of the SDE unit, regulating the amount of SA recirculated to the SDE itself, as represented in Figure 37.

Figure 37 – Preliminary definition of main control loops for SDE section

Concerning the SA concentration section (Figure 38), the control logic conventionally adopted for multi-effect evaporation units has been here assumed: particularly, in each evaporation stage, the pressure, which directly affects L-V equilibrium, is controlled by varying the outlet vapour flowrate. Additionally, it has been hypothesized to control the flowrate of the concentrated SA outlet stream, indirectly affecting its composition, by varying the flowrate of the HTF supplying heat to the first evaporator.

Finally, considering the distillation column, which substantially is a stripping column, the key process parameter to be controlled is the reboiler temperature, which can be regulated by modulating the heat supply to the reboiler.

Figure 38 – Preliminary definition of main control loops for SA concentration section

6.2. Preliminary sizing of the demo plant

To guide the design of the demo plant, a preliminary sizing of the main units has been undertaken. Particularly, based on the process flowsheet of Figure 32, a simplified Block Flow Diagram (BFD) has been elaborated within T2.1 and is shown in Figure 39. The main blocks of interest are:

- the Sulphuric Acid Splitting (SA splitting -Work Package 6);
- the Gas Separation (Work Package 7);
- the Sulphur Dioxide Electrolyzer (SDE - Work Package 5);

Figure 39: Block Flow Diagram of the HySelect demo plant

These blocks have also been colour-coded, yellow being the solar-thermal and solar thermochemical part, green the chemical part and blue the electrochemical part of the HySelect demo plant.

For this BFD the main mass and energy flows have been calculated, for a set target capacity of the demo plant, based on the results of the ASPEN Plus simulations for the reference case of 1 mol SO₂ produced at the SAS reactor. The rationale here is to determine the sizing (boundary conditions) of the power and mass flow requirements of the main process blocks for different target hydrogen production scenarios. The results of these calculations can act as the specifications (upper and lower limits) of the main blocks.

In order to guide the design work and definition of specifications of these blocks, operation scenarios of the HySelect Demo plant are built as cases. These cases are built from a set of certain fixed parameters that cannot be changed, and from a set of parameters that are varied.

The following parameters are considered fixed for all cases:

- a full 2h warm up is required each day, where no chemical production takes place, essentially being the dead time of the system till warmed-up and ready for operation;
- the efficiency of the Jülich solar field is given and fixed at 48%;
- the size (aperture) and efficiency of the centrifugal particle receiver is given and fixed at 750kWth (1.6m) and 80%;

- the hot storage tank losses represent the 10% of the overall tank capacity;
- the capacity of the hot storage tank is fixed at 4MWh.

The first dimension of the parameters that can be varied is the targeted H₂ production. This is defined as the mass of Hydrogen produced, per day of operation, per area of receiver. Following cases have been considered:

- hydrogen production at target of 2.16 kg H₂/day/m² of receiver (project call target);
- hydrogen production at 20% over target;
- hydrogen production at 10% over target.

The second dimension, to be varied is the operational time of the overall plant (solar and chemical part), i.e. the definition of operational day duration. Following cases are considered:

- plant operation of 24h. A full 24h is available to reach production targets. The 24h day is split up into the 2h warm-up, 6h of on-sun charging the hot storage and a full double shift of 16h for the chemical operation of plant. The chemical plant is working in series with the solar plant, i.e. first the hot storage is fully charged for 6h and then it is discharged over 16h.
- plant operation of 10h. Only 10h out of 24h are available to reach production targets. The rest of the hours is considered down-time, no operation takes place. The 10h day is split up into the 2h warm-up, 6h of charging the hot storage, leaving only 2h hours of operation of the chemical plant available to reach the targeted hydrogen production. As before, charging and discharging happens only in a serial fashion.
- plant operation of 8h. Only 8h out of 24h are available to reach production targets, the rest is considered down-time. The 8h day is split up into the 2h warm-up and 6h of charging the hot storage. Here, after the initial warm up, the hot storage is simultaneously charged and discharged, i.e. the solar plant operates in parallel to the chemical plant. From the technical viewpoint this capability of the particle system to be operated in a parallel charge/discharge mode exists without any restraints.

For all operation scenarios considered, the overall demo plant solar-to-fuel efficiency always lies over 12%. Here it is worth underlining the definition of the solar-to-fuel efficiency η_{sol} as the ratio of the High Heating Value of the hydrogen produced to the net energy consumed:

$$\eta_{sol} = \frac{HHV}{Q_{tot} + \frac{E_{tot}}{\eta_{th}}} \quad (\text{eq.1})$$

with Q_{tot} is the net thermal energy demand and E_{tot} the net electricity demand, which is here converted into the corresponding thermal energy input by considering the thermal-to-electrical conversion efficiency η_{th} , conservatively assumed equal to 0.4.

Gathering the above considerations in operational cases, the scenarios considered have been grouped in three cases:

- Case A: target H₂ production, 6h of solar operation, 16h of chemical operation, in series
- Case B: 20% overproduction, 6h of solar operation, 2h of chemical operation, in series
- Case C: 10% overproduction, 6h of solar and chemical operation, in parallel.

The resulting relevant mass and energy flows of the main blocks are summarized in Table 12 below. The operation hours refer to the operation of the chemical plant, the SAS (SAD+STS) reactor power refers to the amount of heat that must be supplied to the reactor, the SDE power refers to the electrical power that must be supplied to the electrolyser and the gas separation refers to the amount (mass) of gases (SO₂, SO₃, H₂SO₄, O₂) exiting the reactor that need to be treated and separated.

Table 12: Initial sizing of main blocks of the HySelect demo plant - Fixed parameters: size of heliostat field, receiver power, thermal storage capacity, 2h start-up, 6h on-sun charging

	production (kg H ₂ /day/m ² receiver)	operation (h)	SAS reactor (kW _{th})	SDE (kW _{el})	gas separation (kg/day)
Case A	2.16	16 (serial)	16	11	170
Case B	2.59	2 (serial)	153	102	204
Case C	2.38	6 (parallel)	47	31	187

7. References

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Appendix

Table 13: Mass and energy balance referred to the SA decomposition section: indirect contact scheme (optimized configuration).

Stream	101	102	103	104	105	106	108	109	111	112	113	114	115
Mole Flow [mol/sec]													
H ₂ O	1.82	1.82	3.06	3.06	4.65	4.65	2.82	1.24	2.00	0.83	2.00	1.95	0.05
H ₂ SO ₄	1.00	1.00	1.71	1.71	0.12	0.12	0.00	0.70	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.59	0.59	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.03	0.97
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.50	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.50
Mole Frac [-]													
H ₂ O	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.73	0.68	0.65	0.64	0.57	1.00	0.57	0.99	0.03
H ₂ SO ₄	0.36	0.36	0.36	0.36	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.36	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.25	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.15	0.23	0.00	0.29	0.00	0.29	0.01	0.64
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.12	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.33
Mass Flow [kg/sec]													
H ₂ O	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.06	0.08	0.08	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.00
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.17	0.17	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.06
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.02
Mass Frac [-]													
H ₂ O	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.38	0.38	0.39	0.24	0.31	0.99	0.31	0.95	0.01
H ₂ SO ₄	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.76	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.57	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.29	0.49	0.00	0.55	0.01	0.55	0.05	0.79
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.12	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.20
Total Flow [mol/sec]													
	2.82	2.82	4.76	4.76	6.35	6.85	4.33	1.94	3.50	0.83	3.50	1.98	1.52
Total Flow [kg/sec]													
	0.13	0.13	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.13	0.09	0.12	0.02	0.12	0.04	0.08
T [C]	25	138	155	295	500	800	180	180	85	85	25	25	25
P [atm]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Vap. Frac	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.43	0.00	1.00
Liq. Frac	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.57	1.00	0.00
Energy consumption [kJ/molso₂]													
SAD reactor	218												
STS reactor	195												
HE2 (rec.) J/molso	383												
HE3 (rec.)	49												
Net energy required	411												

Table 14: Mass and energy balance referred to the SA decomposition section: direct contact scheme with the alternative heat recovery configuration.

Stream	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113
Mole Flow [mol/sec]													
H ₂ O	1.82	1.82	2.82	1.11	1.11	2.46	2.46	2.11	1.82	2.82	2.06	0.76	2.06
H ₂ SO ₄	1.00	1.00	0.00	1.44	1.44	0.09	0.09	0.44	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.25	0.25	1.59	0.59	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	1.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.50	0.00	0.50	0.50	0.00	0.50
Mole Frac													
H ₂ O	0.64	0.64	0.65	0.40	0.40	0.59	0.53	0.49	0.64	0.65	0.58	1.00	0.58
H ₂ SO ₄	0.36	0.36	0.00	0.51	0.51	0.02	0.02	0.10	0.36	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.09	0.38	0.13	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.24	0.24	0.00	0.22	0.25	0.00	0.25
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.12	0.00	0.12	0.14	0.00	0.14
Mass Flow [kg/sec]													
H ₂ O	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.04	0.01	0.04
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.14	0.14	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.13	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.06
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.02
Mass Frac													
H ₂ O	0.25	0.25	0.39	0.11	0.11	0.24	0.24	0.21	0.25	0.39	0.32	0.99	0.32
H ₂ SO ₄	0.75	0.75	0.00	0.78	0.78	0.05	0.05	0.24	0.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.11	0.70	0.26	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.49	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.36	0.00	0.49	0.55	0.01	0.55
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.09	0.00	0.12	0.14	0.00	0.14
Total Flow [mol/sec]													
	2.82	2.82	4.33	2.80	2.80	4.14	4.64	4.30	2.82	4.33	3.57	0.76	3.57
Total Flow [kg/sec]													
	0.13	0.13	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.13	0.13	0.12	0.01	0.12	0.08
T [C]	25	25	165	252	305	500	800	350	127	85	85	85	25
P [atm]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Vap. Frac	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.6	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.8	1.0	0.0	0.4
Liq. Frac	1.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.2	0.0	1.0	0.6
Energy consumption [kJ/molso₂]													
SAD reactor	248												
STD reactor	168												
HE2 (rec.)	44												
HE3 (rec.)	97												

Table 15: Mass and energy balance referred to the SO₂-O₂ separation by compression and liquefaction with cooling at - 46°C (Figure 20)

Stream	201	202	203	204	205	206	207	208	209	210	211	212	213	214	215	216	217
Mole Flow [mol/sec]																	
H ₂ O	0.05	0.00	0.63	0.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.001
H ₂ SO ₄	0.00	0.00	0.37	0.37	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.000
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.000
SO ₂	0.97	0.97	0.00	0.00	0.97	0.97	0.66	0.31	0.66	0.66	0.01	0.64	0.64	0.01	0.64	0.01	0.950
O ₂	0.50	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.00	0.50	0.50	0.49	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.49	0.004
Mole Frac																	
H ₂ O	0.03	0.00	0.63	0.64	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.001
H ₂ SO ₄	0.00	0.00	0.37	0.36	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.000
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.000
SO ₂	0.64	0.66	0.00	0.00	0.66	0.66	0.57	0.99	0.57	0.57	0.03	0.99	0.99	0.57	1.00	0.03	0.994
O ₂	0.33	0.34	0.00	0.00	0.34	0.34	0.43	0.00	0.43	0.43	0.97	0.01	0.01	0.43	0.00	0.97	0.005
Mass Flow [kg/sec]																	
H ₂ O	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.000
H ₂ SO ₄	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.000
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.000
SO ₂	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.061
O ₂	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.000
Mass Frac																	
H ₂ O	0.01	0.00	0.24	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.000
H ₂ SO ₄	0.00	0.00	0.77	0.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.000
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.000
SO ₂	0.79	0.79	0.00	0.00	0.79	0.79	0.72	1.00	0.72	0.72	0.05	0.99	0.99	0.73	1.00	0.05	0.997
O ₂	0.20	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.21	0.21	0.28	0.00	0.28	0.28	0.95	0.01	0.01	0.27	0.00	0.95	0.002
Total Flow [mol/sec]																	
	1.52	1.47	1.00	1.05	1.47	1.47	1.16	0.31	1.16	1.16	0.51	0.65	0.65	0.01	0.64	0.51	0.96
Total Flow [kg/sec]																	
	0.08	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.02	0.06	0.06	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.04	0.02	0.06
T [C]	25.0	26.7	25.0	50.3	50.0	25.0	25.0	25.0	21.4	-46.0	-45.9	-45.9	18.0	25.0	25.0	25.0	25.0
P[atm]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.20
Vap.F rac	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.79	1.00	0.00	0.88	0.44	1.00	0.00	0.01	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.00
Liq. Frac	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.21	0.00	1.00	0.12	0.56	0.00	1.00	0.99	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00
Energy consumption [kJ_{el}/molSO₂]																	
K2.1	10.39																
K2.2	10.89																

Table 16: Mass and energy balance referred to the SO₂-O₂ separation by compression and liquefaction with cooling at - 55°C (Figure 21)

Stream	201	202	203	204	205	206	207	208	209	210	211	212	213	214	215	216	217	218	219	220	221	222
Mole Flow [mol/sec]																						
H ₂ O	0.05	0.00	0.37	0.42	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
H ₂ SO ₄	0.00	0.00	0.39	0.39	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.97	0.97	0.00	0.00	0.97	0.97	0.44	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.36	0.17	0.36	0.36	0.36	0.36	0.00	0.36	0.00	0.00	0.44	0.96
O ₂	0.50	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.50	0.00	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.00	0.01	0.50	0.50	0.01	0.49	0.01	0.49	0.00	0.00	0.01
Mole Frac																						
H ₂ O	0.03	0.00	0.49	0.52	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
H ₂ SO ₄	0.00	0.00	0.51	0.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.64	0.66	0.00	0.00	0.66	0.66	0.99	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.42	0.99	0.98	0.42	0.42	0.98	0.01	0.99	0.01	0.31	0.99	0.99
O ₂	0.33	0.34	0.00	0.00	0.34	0.34	0.01	0.48	0.48	0.48	0.58	0.01	0.02	0.58	0.58	0.02	0.99	0.01	0.99	0.69	0.01	0.01
Mass Flow [kg/sec]																						
H ₂ O	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
H ₂ SO ₄	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.06
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass Frac																						
H ₂ O	0.01	0.00	0.15	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
H ₂ SO ₄	0.00	0.00	0.85	0.83	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.79	0.79	0.00	0.00	0.79	0.79	1.00	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.59	0.99	0.99	0.59	0.59	0.99	0.02	0.99	0.02	0.48	1.00	1.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total Flow [mol/sec]																						
	1.52	1.47	0.76	0.81	1.47	1.47	0.44	1.03	1.03	1.03	0.86	0.17	0.37	0.86	0.86	0.37	0.49	0.36	0.49	0.01	0.44	0.97
Total Flow [kg/sec]																						
	0.08	0.08	0.04	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.03	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.06

T [C]	25.0	27.1	25.0	60.0	50.0	25.0	25.0	25.0	50.0	35.0	35.0	35.0	18.0	29.2	-55	-55	-55	25.0	25.0	25.0	26.0	27.2
P [atm]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0
Vap. Frac	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.7	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.8	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.9	0.6	0.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.0
Liq. Frac	0.0	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.3	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.1	0.4	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	1.0

Energy consumption [kJ_e/mol_{so2}]

K2.1	11.21
K2.2	2.03
K2.3	10.32

Table 17: Mass and energy balance of the H_2SO_4 concentration process based on single evaporation (inlet SA concentration: 15wt%) corresponding to Figure 23.

Stream	401	402	403	404
Mole Flow [mol/s]				
H ₂ O	31.20	31.20	29.39	1.81
H ₂ SO ₄	1.01	1.01	0.01	1.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]				
H ₂ O	0.97	0.97	1.00	0.64
H ₂ SO ₄	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.36
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]				
H ₂ O	0.56	0.56	0.53	0.03
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.10
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]				
H ₂ O	0.85	0.85	1.00	0.25
H ₂ SO ₄	0.15	0.15	0.00	0.75
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total flow [mol/sec]				
	32.21	32.21	29.40	2.81
Total flow [kg/sec]				
	0.66	0.66	0.53	0.13
T [C]	25.0	180.1	180.1	180.1
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Vap. rac	0.00	0.91	1.00	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]				
E4.1		1524		
Total consumption		1524		

Table 18: Mass and energy balance of the H_2SO_4 concentration process based on single evaporation (inlet SA concentration: 25wt%) corresponding to Figure 23.

Stream	401	402	403	404
Mole Flow [mol/s]				
H ₂ O	16.43	16.43	14.64	1.79
H ₂ SO ₄	1.01	1.01	0.01	1.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]				
H ₂ O	0.94	0.94	1.00	0.64
H ₂ SO ₄	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.36
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]				
H ₂ O	0.30	0.30	0.26	0.03
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.10
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]				
H ₂ O	0.75	0.75	1.00	0.25
H ₂ SO ₄	0.25	0.25	0.00	0.75
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total flow [mol/sec]				
	17.44	17.44	14.65	2.79
Total flow [kg/sec]				
T [C]	0.39	0.39	0.26	0.13
P [atm]	25.0	181.0	181.0	181.0
Vap. Frac	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]				
E4.1		825		
Total consumption		825		

Table 19: Mass and energy balance referred to the H_2SO_4 concentration process based on single evaporation and partial heat recovery (inlet SA concentration: 15wt%) corresponding to Figure 24.

Stream	401	402	403	404	405	406
Mole Flow [mol/s]						
H ₂ O	31.20	31.20	31.20	29.39	29.39	1.81
H ₂ SO ₄	1.01	1.01	1.01	0.01	0.01	1.00
SO ₃	0	0	0	0	0	0
SO ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
O ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mole fraction [-]						
H ₂ O	0.97	0.97	0.97	1.00	1.00	0.64
H ₂ SO ₄	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.36
SO ₃	0	0	0	0	0	0
SO ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
O ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mass flow [kg/s]						
H ₂ O	0.56	0.56	0.56	0.53	0.53	0.03
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.10
SO ₃	0	0	0	0	0	0
SO ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
O ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mass fraction [-]						
H ₂ O	0.85	0.85	0.85	1.00	1.00	0.25
H ₂ SO ₄	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.75
SO ₃	0	0	0	0	0	0
SO ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
O ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total flow [mol/sec]						
	32.21	32.21	32.21	29.40	29.40	2.81
Total flow [kg/sec]						
	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.53	0.53	0.13
T [C]	25.0	102.0	180.1	180.1	100.2	180.1
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Vap. Frac	0.00	0.00	0.91	1.00	0.91	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]						
E4.1 (recovered)	185					
E.4.2	1337					
Total consumptior	1337					

Table 20: Mass and energy balance referred to the H_2SO_4 concentration process based on single evaporation and partial heat recovery (inlet SA concentration: 25wt%) corresponding to Figure 24.

Stream	401	402	403	404	405	406
Mole Flow [mol/s]						
H ₂ O	16.46	16.46	16.46	14.64	14.64	1.82
H ₂ SO ₄	1.01	1.01	1.01	0.01	0.01	1.00
SO ₃	0	0	0	0	0	0
SO ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
O ₂						
Mole fraction [-]						
H ₂ O	0.94	0.94	0.94	1.00	1.00	0.64
H ₂ SO ₄	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.36
SO ₃	0	0	0	0	0	0
SO ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
O ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mass flow [kg/s]						
H ₂ O	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.26	0.26	0.03
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.10
SO ₃	0	0	0	0	0	0
SO ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
O ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mass fraction [-]						
H ₂ O	0.75	0.75	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.25
H ₂ SO ₄	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.75
SO ₃	0	0	0	0	0	0
SO ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
O ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total flow [mol/sec]						
	17.47	17.47	17.47	14.65	14.65	2.82
Total flow [kg/sec]						
	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.26	0.26	0.13
T [C]	25.0	106.0	180.1	180.1	100.2	180.1
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Vap. rac	0.00	0.00	0.84	1.00	0.89	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H₂SO₄}]						
E4.1 (recovered)	105					
E.4.2	690					
Total consumption	690					

Table 21: Mass and energy balance of the H_2SO_4 concentration process based on single evaporation and optimized heat recovery (use of water steam compression. inlet SA concentration: 15wt%) corresponding to Figure 25.

Stream	401	402	403	404	405	406	407
Mole Flow [mol/s]							
H ₂ O	31.20	31.20	31.20	29.39	29.39	29.39	1.81
H ₂ SO ₄	1.01	1.01	1.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	1.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]							
H ₂ O	0.97	0.97	0.97	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.64
H ₂ SO ₄	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.36
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]							
H ₂ O	0.56	0.56	0.56	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.03
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]							
H ₂ O	0.85	0.85	0.85	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.25
H ₂ SO ₄	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.75
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total flow [mol/sec]							
	32.21	32.21	32.21	29.40	29.40	29.40	2.81
Total flow [kg/sec]							
	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.13
T [C]	25.00	41.00	180.08	180.08	336.81	83.21	37.28
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	2.60	2.60	1.00
Vap. rac	0.00	0.00	0.91	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]							
E4.1 (recovered)			40				
E.4.2 (recovered)			1482				
K.4.1 (electrical)			169				
Total consumption (electrical)			169				

Table 22: Mass and energy balance of the H_2SO_4 concentration process based on single evaporation and optimized heat recovery (use of water steam compression. inlet SA concentration: 25wt%) corresponding to Figure 25.

Stream	401	402	403	404	405	406	407
Mole Flow [mol/s]							
H ₂ O	16.46	16.46	16.46	14.64	14.64	14.64	1.82
H ₂ SO ₄	1.01	1.01	1.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	1.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]							
H ₂ O	0.94	0.94	0.94	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.64
H ₂ SO ₄	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.36
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]							
H ₂ O	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.03
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]							
H ₂ O	0.75	0.75	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.25
H ₂ SO ₄	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.75
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total flow [mol/sec]							
	17.47	17.47	17.47	14.65	14.65	14.65	2.82
Total flow [kg/sec]							
	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.13
T [C]	25.00	55.00	180.08	180.08	343.83	71.15	37.97
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	2.60	2.60	1.00
Vap. rac	0.00	0.00	0.84	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]							
E4.1 (recovered)			39.00				
E.4.2 (recovered)			755.00				
K.4.1 (electrical)			87.00				
Total consumption (electrical)			87.00				

Table 23: Mass and energy balance referred to the H_2SO_4 concentration process based on distillation and optimized heat recovery (use of water steam compression. inlet SA concentration: 15wt%); corresponding to Figure 27.

Stream	401	402	403	404	405	406	407	408
Mole Flow [mol/s]								
H ₂ O	30.85	30.85	30.85	29.04	29.04	1.81	29.04	1.81
H ₂ SO ₄	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]								
H ₂ O	0.97	0.97	0.97	1.00	1.00	0.64	1.00	0.64
H ₂ SO ₄	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.00	0.36
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]								
H ₂ O	0.56	0.56	0.56	0.52	0.52	0.03	0.52	0.03
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.10
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]								
H ₂ O	0.85	0.85	0.85	1.00	1.00	0.25	1.00	0.25
H ₂ SO ₄	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.75	0.00	0.75
SO ₃	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SO ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
O ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total flow [mol/sec]								
	31.85	31.85	31.85	29.04	29.04	2.81	29.04	2.81
Total flow [kg/sec]								
	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.52	0.52	0.13	0.52	0.13
T [C]	25.00	41.00	124.00	124.00	264.12	180.19	129.20	39.03
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	2.60	1.00	2.60	1.00
Vap. rac	0.00	0.00	0.79	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.05	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]								
E4.1 (recovered)				39.81				
E.4.2 (recovered)				1218.29				
K.4.1 (electrical)				143.33				
R.4.1 (thermal)				191.10				
Total consumption				334.43				
Total consumption as primary source				549.42				

Table 24: Mass and energy balance referred to the H_2SO_4 concentration process based on distillation and optimized heat recovery (use of water steam compression. inlet SA concentration: 25wt%). corresponding to Figure 27.

Stream	401	402	403	404	405	406	407	408
Mole Flow [mol/s]								
H ₂ O	16.39	16.39	16.39	14.57	14.57	1.82	14.57	1.82
H ₂ SO ₄	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]								
H ₂ O	0.94	0.94	0.94	1.00	1.00	0.64	1.00	0.64
H ₂ SO ₄	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.00	3.83
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]								
H ₂ O	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.26	0.26	0.03	0.26	0.03
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.10
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]								
H ₂ O	0.75	0.75	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.25	1.00	0.25
H ₂ SO ₄	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.75	0.00	0.75
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total flow [mol/sec]								
	17.39	17.39	17.39	14.57	14.57	2.82	14.57	2.82
Total flow [kg/sec]								
	0.39	0.39	0.39	0.26	0.26	0.13	0.26	0.13
T [C]	25.00	55.00	142.00	142.00	287.61	180.06	129.20	38.81
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	2.60	1.00	2.60	1.00
Vap. frac	0.00	0.00	0.74	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.02	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]								
E4.1 (recovered)				39.00				
E.4.2 (recovered)				643.00				
K.4.1 (electrical)				74.00				
R.4.1 (thermal)				87.00				
Total consumption				161.00				
Total consumption as primary source				263.00				

Table 25: Mass and energy balance referred to the H_2SO_4 concentration process based on multi evaporation method (inlet SA concentration: 15wt%, outlet SA concentration: 75%).)

Stream	401	402	403	404	405	406	407	408	409	410	411	412	413	414
Mole Flow [mol/s]														
H ₂ O	30.8	1.81	12.4	21.9	16.11	10.6	9.52	8.87	9.52	10.6	16.1	12.4	21.9	9.52
H ₂ SO ₄	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]														
H ₂ O	0.97	0.64	0.93	0.96	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.93	0.96	1.00
H ₂ SO ₄	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]														
H ₂ O	0.55	0.03	0.22	0.40	0.29	0.19	0.17	0.16	0.17	0.19	0.29	0.22	0.40	0.17
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]														
H ₂ O	0.85	0.25	0.69	0.80	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.69	0.80	1.00
H ₂ SO ₄	0.15	0.75	0.31	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.31	0.20	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total flow [mol/sec]														
	31.80	2.81	13.41	22.93	16.11	10.60	9.52	8.87	9.52	10.60	16.11	13.41	22.93	9.52
Total flow [kg/sec]														
	0.65	0.13	0.32	0.50	0.29	0.19	0.17	0.16	0.17	0.19	0.29	0.32	0.5	0.17
T [C]	25.00	180.31	67.66	33.25	190.00	180.31	67.66	33.25	60.31	100.0	190.00	67.66	33.25	60.31
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	0.20	0.04	12.37	1.00	0.20	0.04	0.20	1.00	12.37	1.00	0.20	1.00

Vap. Frac.	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]														
E.4.1														553
E.4.2 (recovered)														463
E.4.3 (recovered)														407
Total consumption														553

Table 26: Mass and energy balance referred to the H₂SO₄ concentration process based on multi effect evaporation method (inlet SA concentration: 25wt%, outlet SA concentration: 75%).

Stream	401	402	403	404	405	406	407	408	409	410	411	412	413	414
Mole Flow [mol/s]														
H ₂ O	16.39	1.82	7.35	12.10	8.47	5.54	4.74	4.29	4.74	5.54	8.47	7.35	12.10	4.74
H ₂ SO ₄	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]														
H ₂ O	0.94	0.64	0.88	0.92	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.88	0.92	1.00
H ₂ SO ₄	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]														
H ₂ O	0.30	0.03	0.13	0.22	0.15	0.10	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.15	0.13	0.22	0.09
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]														
H ₂ O	0.75	0.25	0.57	0.69	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.57	0.69	1.00
H ₂ SO ₄	0.25	0.75	0.43	0.31	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.43	0.31	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total flow [mol/sec]														
	17.39	2.82	8.36	13.10	8.47	5.54	4.74	4.29	4.74	5.54	8.47	8.36	13.10	4.74
Total flow [kg/sec]														
	0.39	0.13	0.23	0.32	0.15	0.10	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.15	0.23	0.32	0.09
T [C]	25.00	180.13	75.37	37.21	190.00	180.13	75.37	37.21	60.31	100.02	190.00	75.37	37.21	60.31
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	0.20	0.04	12.37	1.00	0.20	0.04	0.20	1.00	12.37	1.00	0.20	1.00

Vap. frac	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]														
E.4.1				309										
E.4.2 (recovered)				242										
E.4.3 (recovered)				204										
Total consumption				309										

Table 27: Mass and energy balance referred to the H_2SO_4 concentration process based on multi effect evaporation method (inlet SA concentration: 45wt%; outlet SA concentration: 70.6%).

Stream	401	402	403	404	405	406	407	408	409	410	411	412	413	414
Mole Flow [mol/s]														
H ₂ O	6.68	2.27	4.25	5.66	16.67	1.98	1.41	1.02	1.41	1.98	16.67	4.25	5.66	1.41
H ₂ SO ₄	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]														
H ₂ O	0.87	0.69	0.81	0.85	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.81	0.85	1.00
H ₂ SO ₄	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]														
H ₂ O	0.12	0.04	0.08	0.10	0.30	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.30	0.08	0.10	0.03
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]														
H ₂ O	0.55	0.29	0.44	0.51	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.44	0.51	1.00
H ₂ SO ₄	0.45	0.71	0.56	0.49	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.56	0.49	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total flow [mol/sec]														
	7.68	3.28	5.25	6.66	16.67	1.98	1.41	1.02	1.41	1.98	16.67	5.25	6.66	1.41
Total flow [kg/sec]														
	0.22	0.14	0.17	0.20	0.30	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.30	0.17	0.20	0.03
T [C]	25.00	164.93	89.47	49.50	190.00	164.93	89.47	49.50	60.31	100.00	190.00	89.47	49.50	89.47
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	0.20	0.04	12.37	1.00	0.20	0.04	0.20	1.00	12.37	1.00	0.20	1.00

Vap. frac	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.80	0.00	0.00	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]														
E.4.1	122.90													
E.4.2 (recovered)														
E.4.3 (recovered)														
Total consumption	122.90													

Table 28: Mass and energy balance referred to the H_2SO_4 concentration process based on multi effect evaporation method (inlet SA concentration: 45wt%; outlet SA concentration: 75%).

Stream	401	402	403	404	405	406	407	408	409	410	411	412	413	414
Mole Flow [mol/s]														
H ₂ O	6.68	1.82	3.95	5.51	16.67	2.13	1.56	1.17	1.56	2.13	6.68	3.95	5.51	1.56
H ₂ SO ₄	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]														
H ₂ O	0.87	0.64	0.80	0.85	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.80	0.85	1.00
H ₂ SO ₄	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]														
H ₂ O	0.12	0.03	0.07	0.10	0.30	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.30	0.07	0.10	0.03
H ₂ SO ₄	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]														
H ₂ O	0.55	0.25	0.42	0.50	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.42	0.50	1.00
H ₂ SO ₄	0.45	0.75	0.58	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.58	0.50	0.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total flow [mol/sec]														
	7.68	2.82	4.95	6.52	16.67	2.13	1.56	1.17	1.56	2.13	16.67	4.95	6.52	1.56
Total flow [kg/sec]														
	0.22	0.13	0.17	0.20	0.30	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.30	0.17	0.20	0.03

T [C]	25.00	180.22	92.03	50.10	190.00	180.22	92.03	50.10	60.31	100.02	25.00	92.03	50.10	92.03
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	0.20	0.04	12.37	1.00	0.20	0.04	0.20	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.20	1.00
Vap. frac	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]														
E.4.1		135.20												
E.4.2 (recovered)														
E.4.3 (recovered)														
Total consumption		135.20												

Table 29: Mass and energy balance referred to the H_2SO_4 concentration by distillation up to 85wt% (inlet SA concentration: 70.6wt%).

Stream	4101	4102	4103
Mole Flow [mol/s]			
H ₂ O	2.2682	1.31	0.96
H ₂ SO ₄	1.00	0.00	1.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]			
H ₂ O	0.69	1.00	0.49
H ₂ SO ₄	0.31	0.00	0.51
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]			
H ₂ O	40.86	23.58	17.28
H ₂ SO ₄	98.08	0.00	98.08
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]			
H ₂ O	0.29	1.00	0.15
H ₂ SO ₄	0.71	0.00	0.85
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total flow [mol/sec]			
	3.27	1.31	1.96
Total flow [kg/sec]			
	138.94	23.58	115.36
T [C]	180.00	100.00	227.99
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	1.00
Vap. Frac	0.14	0.00	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]			
C.4.10 reboiler		94.17	
C.4.10 condenser		-93.82	
Total consumption		94.17	

Table 30: Mass and energy balance referred to the H_2SO_4 concentration by distillation up to 85wt% (inlet SA concentration: 75wt%).

Stream	4101	4102	4103
Mole Flow [mol/s]			
H ₂ O	1.8147	0.85	0.96
H ₂ SO ₄	1.00	0.00	1.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]			
H ₂ O	0.64	1.00	0.49
H ₂ SO ₄	0.36	0.00	0.51
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]			
H ₂ O	32.69	15.40	17.29
H ₂ SO ₄	98.08	0.00	98.08
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]			
H ₂ O	0.25	1.00	0.15
H ₂ SO ₄	0.75	0.00	0.85
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total flow [mol/sec]			
	2.81	0.85	1.96
Total flow [kg/sec]			
	130.77	15.40	115.37
T [C]	180.00	100.00	227.94
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	1.00
Vap. Frac	0.00	0.00	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]			
C.4.10 reboiler		81.13	
C.4.10 condenser		-61.13	
Total consumption		81.13	

Table 31: Mass and energy balance referred to the H_2SO_4 concentration by distillation (no top condenser) up to 85wt (inlet SA concentration: 75wt%).

Stream	4101	4102	4103
Mole Flow [mol/s]			
H ₂ O	1.82	0.86	0.96
H ₂ SO ₄	1.00	0.00	1.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]			
H ₂ O	0.64	1.00	0.49
H ₂ SO ₄	0.36	0.00	0.51
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]			
H ₂ O	32.79	15.45	17.34
H ₂ SO ₄	98.36	0.03	98.33
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]			
H ₂ O	0.25	1.00	0.15
H ₂ SO ₄	0.75	0.00	0.85
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total flow [mol/sec]			
	2.82	0.86	1.96
Total flow [kg/sec]			
	131.14	15.48	115.66
T [C]	180.00	100.00	227.94
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	1.00
Vap. Frac	0.00	0.00	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]			
C.4.10 reboiler		57.60	
C.4.10 condenser		0.00	
Total consumption		57.60	

Table 32: Mass and energy balance referred to the H_2SO_4 concentration by distillation (no top condenser) up to 85wt% (inlet SA concentration: 70.6wt%).

Stream	4101	4102	4103
Mole Flow [mol/s]			
H ₂ O	2.27	1.31	0.96
H ₂ SO ₄	1.00	0.00	1.00
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mole fraction [-]			
H ₂ O	0.69	1.00	0.49
H ₂ SO ₄	0.31	0.00	0.51
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass flow [kg/s]			
H ₂ O	40.98	23.65	17.33
H ₂ SO ₄	98.36	0.01	98.35
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mass fraction [-]			
H ₂ O	0.29	1.00	0.15
H ₂ SO ₄	0.71	0.00	0.85
SO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
O ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total flow [mol/sec]			
	3.28	1.31	1.96
Total flow [kg/sec]			
	139.34	23.66	115.69
T [C]	164.90	164.90	227.98
P [atm]	1.00	1.00	1.00
Vap. Frac	0.00	1.00	0.00
Energy consumptions [kJ/mol_{H2SO4}]			
C.4.10 reboiler		83.7	
C.4.10 condenser		0.00	
Total consumption		83.7	